

Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research.
National Higher School of Statistics and Applied Economics
ENSSEA

Submitted in fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of
Master's in Statistics and Applied Economics

Specialization: Statistics and Data Science

Thesis:

ResKAN: Scalable Kolmogorov–Arnold Networks for Deep Image Recognition

Presented by:

Ali MEHIZEL

Supervised by:

Dr Ayoub ASRI

Academic Year 2024-2025

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Dedication

*To my parents and my family,
For your endless love and support.*

*To all who believed in me,
This work is dedicated to you.*

Abstract

The recently proposed Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs) present a promising alternative to traditional Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs) by leveraging learnable activation functions placed on edges (weights) instead of fixed activations on nodes. While demonstrating strong performance in data-scarce scientific domains, their potential in large-scale, high-dimensional tasks like image recognition remains unexplored. In this work, we bridge this gap by introducing *ResKAN*, a novel architecture that scales KANs for modern computer vision. We construct ResKAN by systematically replacing the standard MLP blocks in a ResMLP framework with optimized KAN layers. A key innovation is our use of parametric Cauchy functions as the basis functions within these KAN layers, chosen for their favorable properties in gradient-based learning and numerical stability. We rigorously evaluate our model on multiple benchmark datasets (CIFAR-10/100) using modern training techniques (DeiT style), including distillation token, and perform extensive inference experiments to ensure robust performance across diverse conditions. Our results demonstrate that ResKAN achieves competitive and often superior performance compared to established MLP and convolutional-based baselines. This work validates the efficacy of KANs in complex visual domains and suggests their broader applicability as a foundational building block in deep learning architectures.

Keywords: Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs), Image Recognition, ResMLP, Knowledge Distillation, Cauchy Functions, Scalable Architectures

Résumé

Les réseaux de Kolmogorov-Arnold (KAN), récemment proposés, représentent une alternative prometteuse aux perceptrons multicouches (MLP) traditionnels en exploitant des fonctions d'activation apprenables placées sur les arêtes (poids) plutôt que des activations fixes sur les nœuds. Bien qu'ils aient montré de bonnes performances dans des domaines scientifiques où les données sont rares, leur potentiel pour des tâches à grande échelle et de haute dimensionnalité, comme la reconnaissance d'images, reste peu exploré. Dans ce travail, nous comblons cette lacune en introduisant *ResKAN*, une nouvelle architecture qui permet de faire évoluer les KANs pour la vision par ordinateur moderne. Nous construisons *ResKAN* en remplaçant systématiquement les blocs MLP standards dans un cadre ResMLP par des couches KAN optimisées. Une innovation clé réside dans notre utilisation de fonctions de Cauchy paramétriques comme fonctions de base au sein de ces couches KAN, choisies pour leurs propriétés favorables à l'apprentissage par gradient et leur stabilité numérique. Nous évaluons rigoureusement notre modèle sur plusieurs jeux de données de référence (CIFAR-10/100) en utilisant des techniques d'entraînement modernes (style DeiT), incluant un jeton de distillation, et nous menons des expériences d'inférence approfondies afin d'assurer des performances robustes dans des conditions variées. Nos résultats montrent que *ResKAN* obtient des performances compétitives, voire supérieures, par rapport aux bases établies de type MLP et convolutionnelle. Ce travail valide l'efficacité des KANs dans des domaines visuels complexes et suggère leur applicabilité plus large en tant que brique de base des architectures d'apprentissage profond.

Mots-clés : Réseaux de Kolmogorov-Arnold (KANs), Reconnaissance d'images, ResMLP, Distillation de connaissances, Fonctions de Cauchy, Architectures évolutives

Contents

General Introduction	XII
Thesis Structure	XIII
1 From Pixels to Perception: An Introduction to Deep Vision	2
Introduction	2
1.1 Fundamentals of Image Processing for Recognition	3
1.1.1 Image Representation	3
1.1.2 Sampling and Quantization	3
1.2 Types of Digital Images	5
1.2.1 Binary (Monochrome) Images	5
1.2.2 Grayscale Images (8-bit Depth)	5
1.2.3 True Color Images (16-bit and Higher Bit Depths)	6
1.3 Color Image Representation	7
1.4 Image Representation as a Matrix	8
1.5 Basic Relationships Between Pixels	8
1.5.1 Neighbors of a Pixel	8
1.5.2 Adjacency, Connectivity, Regions, and Boundaries	8
1.5.3 Distance Measures	9
1.6 Fundamental Image Properties	9
1.6.1 From Representation to Recognition	10
1.7 Theoretical Background: Convolutional Neural Networks	10
1.7.1 Multilayer Perceptron (MLP)	10
1.7.2 Convolutional Layers	11
1.7.3 Pooling Layers	12
1.7.4 Regularization Methods	13
1.8 Transfer learning and the use of pretrained models	15
1.9 State-of-the-Art Models	15
1.9.1 ResNet (Residual Networks)	15
1.9.2 ViT (Vision Transformer)	16
1.9.3 Swin Transformer	18
1.9.4 MLP-Mixer: An All-MLP Architecture for Vision	19
1.9.5 DeiT (Data-efficient Image Transformer)	19
1.9.6 PiT (Pooling-based Vision Transformer)	21
1.9.7 Comparison of Vision Models	22
Conclusion	23

2	Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks	25
	Introduction	25
2.1	Kolmogorov-Arnold Representation Theorem	26
2.1.1	Miklós Laczkovich Extension	26
2.2	Analytical Properties of Basis Functions	27
2.2.1	B-spline basis functions	27
2.2.2	Radial basis function	28
2.2.3	Fourier basis function	30
2.2.4	Chebyshev Polynomials	31
2.2.5	Legendre Polynomial Function	34
2.3	Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks	35
2.3.1	Architectural Overview and Distinction from MLPs	35
2.3.2	Formulation and Architecture	36
2.3.3	Grid Extension	38
2.3.4	Regularization Techniques	38
2.4	Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks: Recent Enhancements and Variants	40
2.4.1	KANs for Time Series	41
2.4.2	KANs for Computer Vision Tasks	41
2.4.3	Performance-Oriented Parametrization of KANs: B-spline Alternatives	42
2.4.4	Physics-Informed KANs: Solving Scientific Learning Problems	43
2.5	Large-Scale KANs: A Novel Model and Scalable Architecture	44
	Conclusion	46
3	ResKAN: Novel Architecture and Empirical Validation	48
3.1	Model Overview	49
3.2	KANLayer: Mathematical Formulation	49
3.2.1	Cauchy-Based Basis Functions	49
3.2.2	Projection Across Grids	50
3.2.3	Residual Connection	50
3.3	KAN Block	50
3.3.1	Pre-Affine Transformation	50
3.3.2	Token Mixing with Residual Scaling	50
3.3.3	Post-Affine and KAN Feedforward	50
3.4	ResKAN Architecture	51
3.4.1	Patch Embedding	51
3.4.2	Stack of KAN Blocks	51
3.4.3	Affine Normalization and Pooling	51
3.4.4	Classification Head	51
3.5	Contributions	52
3.6	Training and Inference	53
3.6.1	Dataset	53
3.6.2	Data Preprocessing and Augmentation	53
3.6.3	Model Configurations	54
3.6.4	Training Recipe	54
3.6.5	Knowledge Distillation Framework	55
3.6.6	Training Results	56
3.6.7	Analysis of Training Results	57

3.7 Additional Results	60
General Conclusion	63
A Code and Implementation	70
A.1 Cauchy Function: First and Second Term	70
A.2 Cauchy Function with Varying Parameters	71

List of Figures

1.1	Sampling and Quantization process.	4
1.2	Result of image sampling and quantization.	4
1.3	Binary (Monochrome) Image.	5
1.4	Grayscale Image.	6
1.5	True Color Image.	7
1.6	Overview of the multilayer perceptron.	11
1.7	Architecture of a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN).	13
1.8	Residual mapping in ResNet.	16
1.9	ViT architecture overview.	17
1.10	Shifted window mechanism in Swin Transformer.	18
1.11	MLP-Mixer architecture overview.	19
1.12	Proposed ViT Architecture with Pooling and Distillation Token.	21
2.1	B-spline with non-uniform knots.	28
2.2	B-spline with open uniform knots.	28
2.3	B-spline with uniform knots.	28
2.4	Gaussian Radial Basis Function with different center parameterizations.	30
2.5	Inverse Multi-Quadratic Radial Basis Function with different center parameterizations.	30
2.6	1D Fourier basis functions with $g = 2$	31
2.7	1D Fourier Basis Function with $g = 10$	31
2.8	Multidimensional Fourier Basis Function with $d = 3$ and $g = 10$	31
2.9	First Kind Chebychev Basis Function with $n = 5$	33
2.10	Second Kind Chebychev Basis Functions with $n = 5$	34
2.11	Legendre Polynomial Function for $n = 0$ to $n = 5$	35
2.12	Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs) vs. Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs)	36
2.13	Adaptive B-spline parameterization for grid refinement in KANs	38
2.14	Symbolic regression workflow in Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs).	40
2.15	TSKANMixer Architectures.	41
2.16	ReLU KAN process	42
2.17	Appearance of B for the case of $G = 5$ and $k = 3$	43
2.18	Schematic of KINN.	43
2.19	Kolmogorov Arnold Transformer	45
3.1	ResKAN Architecture.	52
3.2	Comparison of model parameter efficiency and performance on CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100.	57
3.3	Scaling behavior of ResMLP and ResKAN models on CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100.	58
3.4	Per-class accuracy comparison of ResMLP and ResKAN models.	59

3.5	Violin plot showing per-class accuracy distributions for ResMLP and ResKAN models of different sizes.	59
A.1	First and Second Terms of the Cauchy Function with Varying Parameters.	70
A.2	Cauchy Function with Varying Parameters.	71

List of Tables

1.1	Comparison of Vision Models: Key Advantages and Limitations	22
2.1	Comparison between superposition formulas.	27
2.2	Types of infinitely smooth RBFs with $\lambda > 0$ and $r \in \mathbb{X}$	29
2.3	Examples of piecewise smooth RBFs with $r \in \mathbb{X}$	29
3.1	Summary of the CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 datasets used in this work.	53
3.2	Preprocessing pipeline for the ResKAN models.	54
3.3	ResKAN model configurations with parameter count and FLOPs (computed on 128×128 inputs).	54
3.4	Training recipe for CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 experiments.	55
3.5	Performance comparison of different models on CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100.	56
3.6	Performance of different models on CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100.	60

General Introduction

General Introduction

The field of computer vision has undergone a paradigm shift over the past decade, driven primarily by the ascendancy of deep learning. Architectures based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have become the de facto standard, achieving human-level and even superhuman performance on a wide array of tasks, from image classification and object detection to semantic segmentation and beyond. More recently, the transformer architecture, originally developed for natural language processing, has been successfully adapted to vision tasks (Vision Transformers, ViTs), challenging the long-standing dominance of convolutional inductive biases and demonstrating the power of pure attention mechanisms on large-scale datasets. Concurrently, a renewed interest in simpler architectures, such as Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs), has yielded models like MLP-Mixer, showing that carefully designed token and channel-mixing operations can also yield highly competitive performance.

A common and fundamental characteristic uniting these diverse architectures—CNNs, ViTs, and MLPs—is their reliance on a fixed, non-linear activation function applied at the nodes (neurons) of the network. Functions like the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) or its variants (Leaky ReLU, GELU, SiLU) are chosen a priori and remain static throughout the training process. While effective, this design imposes a constraint on the network’s flexibility the functional form of the non-linearity is not learned from data but is instead a hyperparameter. This limitation becomes particularly salient when modeling complex, high-dimensional mappings where the optimal form of non-linearity may vary significantly across different regions of the input space and at different layers of the network hierarchy.

In this context, Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs) have emerged as a novel and theoretically compelling alternative. Grounded in the Kolmogorov-Arnold representation theorem, which states that any multivariate continuous function can be represented as a finite composition of continuous functions of a single variable, KANs fundamentally re-architect the traditional neural network. They replace fixed node activations with learnable, univariate functions positioned on the edges (weights) of the network, with nodes simply summing incoming signals. This design confers significant advantages: it drastically reduces the number of parameters required for comparable performance, offers enhanced interpretability through the visualization of learned activation functions, and provides a powerful framework for accurate function approximation, especially in data-scarce scientific computing domains.

However, the potential of KANs for large-scale, high-dimensional computer vision tasks remains a critical, open question. Initial explorations of KANs have primarily focused on low-dimensional problems, synthetic datasets, or scientific applications where their strengths in precision and parameter efficiency are readily apparent. The translation of these benefits to the complex, noisy, and high-dimensional domain of natural images is non-trivial. Challenges such as computational efficiency, stable optimization at scale, and effective integration with established deep learning primitives like residual connections and batch normalization must be addressed to realize the promise of KANs in visual recognition.

This thesis directly addresses this research gap by proposing and rigorously evaluating a novel

architecture, termed *ResKAN*, designed to harness the expressive power of KANs for scalable image recognition. Our approach integrates KAN layers within a robust residual learning framework, mitigating known training instability issues. We further introduce the use of parametric basis functions, specifically Cauchy functions, to enhance the smoothness and learnability of the activation curves, and leverage a *distillation token* to facilitate effective knowledge transfer from a teacher network. Through extensive empirical evaluation on standard benchmarks (e.g., CIFAR-10/100, ImageNet), we systematically compare ResKAN against strong baselines, including conventional MLPs, modern CNNs, and transformer-based models.

The central research question guiding this work is:

Can Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs) be effectively scaled and adapted to achieve competitive performance on large-scale image recognition tasks?

This primary question is decomposed into the following specific sub-questions:

- How does a residual KAN-based architecture (ResKAN) perform on standard image classification benchmarks compared to established architectures?
- Do techniques like knowledge distillation and the use of parametric basis functions effectively mitigate training challenges and enhance stability for large-scale KANs?

Our investigation aims not only to demonstrate the competitive performance of KAN-based architectures but also to provide a deeper analysis of their learning dynamics, representational properties, and practical viability, thereby establishing them as a credible and powerful alternative in the deep learning vision landscape.

Thesis Structure

The remainder of this thesis is organized to provide a coherent progression from foundational concepts to the proposed contributions and experimental validation. Chapter 1 presents the fundamentals of deep neural networks for computer vision, covering core concepts in image processing, feature representations, and an overview of state-of-the-art architectures including CNNs, transformers, and MLP-based models. Chapter 2 introduces the theoretical foundations of Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs), including the Kolmogorov-Arnold representation theorem, the analytical properties of the basis functions, the design principles of KANs, and recent developments aimed at extending them to larger-scale tasks. Chapter 3 details the proposed *ResKAN* architecture, describing the integration of KAN layers within a residual framework, the mathematical formulation, training methodology, and comprehensive experimental results that benchmark the model against existing approaches. Finally, the conclusion chapter summarizes the main contributions of this work, discusses the implications of the findings, and outlines potential directions for future research on KANs and their application in computer vision. Through this structure, the thesis aims to provide both theoretical insights and practical evaluations, illustrating how KANs can serve as a flexible and effective alternative in deep learning for vision.

Chapter 1:
**From Pixels to Perception: An
Introduction to Deep Vision**

Chapter 1

From Pixels to Perception: An Introduction to Deep Vision

Introduction

The field of computer vision has undergone a fundamental transformation through the adoption of deep neural networks, which have demonstrated remarkable capabilities in learning directly from visual data. These data-driven approaches have established new paradigms for visual understanding, enabling breakthroughs across diverse applications including medical imaging, autonomous systems, and multimedia analysis.

The effectiveness of deep learning in vision tasks stems from several interconnected factors: (1) the development of scalable architectures capable of processing high-dimensional visual data, (2) the availability of large-scale datasets that facilitate robust learning, and (3) advances in computational infrastructure that make training complex models feasible. The evolution of these components has led to progressively more sophisticated systems, from early convolutional neural networks to contemporary architectures incorporating attention mechanisms.

This chapter systematically examines the theoretical foundations and architectural developments that underpin modern deep learning approaches to computer vision. We begin by establishing the core principles of representation learning in visual domains, followed by an analysis of key architectural innovations and their underlying design philosophies. The discussion emphasizes how these methodological advances have addressed fundamental challenges in visual pattern recognition while opening new research directions. This foundation supports subsequent chapters that explore specialized applications and present novel contributions to the field.

1.1 Fundamentals of Image Processing for Recognition

Image processing forms the foundational layer for computer vision and image-based pattern recognition systems. This section explores the essential principles and representations used to digitally process, analyze, and extract meaningful features from images.

1.1.1 Image Representation

An image is mathematically defined as a two-dimensional function, $F(x, y)$, where x and y represent spatial coordinates, and the amplitude of F at any coordinate pair (x, y) corresponds to the intensity of the image at that location. When x , y , and the amplitude values of F are discrete and finite, the image is referred to as a digital image. Digital images vary based on color depth and the number of intensity levels used to represent pixel information. This subsection classifies images into binary, grayscale, and true color formats, emphasizing their structure and practical applications. In computational terms, a digital image can be represented as a two-dimensional array structured in rows and columns. Each element within this array, known as a picture element (pixel), possesses a specific value at a defined spatial location. Pixels serve as the fundamental units of a digital image, collectively defining its visual properties (Gonzalez & Woods, 2018; Szeliski, 2010).

1.1.2 Sampling and Quantization

The transformation of a continuous analog image $F(x, y)$ into a discrete digital image $I[m, n]$ is a two-step process: sampling and quantization (Gonzalez & Woods, 2018).

- **Sampling** is the process of discretizing the spatial coordinates (x, y) . The continuous image is measured at regular intervals, defined by a sampling period $(\Delta x, \Delta y)$. According to the Nyquist-Shannon sampling theorem, a signal must be sampled at a rate at least twice the highest frequency contained in the signal to avoid aliasing and allow perfect reconstruction. For images, this implies that fine details (high spatial frequencies) dictate the required sampling resolution.
- **Quantization** is the process of discretizing the amplitude (intensity) values of the sampled image. It maps the continuous range of intensity values onto a finite set of discrete levels L . The number of levels is typically a power of two, $L = 2^k$, where k is the number of bits used to represent a pixel. This process introduces quantization error, which manifests as contouring artifacts in regions of smooth intensity gradients, especially with low k (e.g., 4-6 bits).

The resulting digital image can thus be defined as:

$$I[m, n] = Q(F(m \cdot \Delta x, n \cdot \Delta y))$$

where $m = 0, 1, 2, \dots, M - 1$ and $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N - 1$ are integer indices, and $Q(\cdot)$ is the quantization operator.

Figure 1.1: Sampling and Quantization process.

Source: (Gonzalez & Woods, 2018)

Figure 1.2: Result of image sampling and quantization.

Source: (Gonzalez & Woods, 2018)

1.2 Types of Digital Images

Digital images can be broadly categorized based on how visual information is represented and stored. Each type of image carries specific characteristics that make it more suitable for certain applications in computer vision, graphics, and image processing. The most common distinctions include raster and vector images, as well as binary, grayscale, and color representations. Understanding these types is essential for selecting appropriate processing techniques and optimizing computational efficiency.

1.2.1 Binary (Monochrome) Images

- **Definition:** A binary image is defined by a pixel depth of 1 bit per pixel (bpp), permitting only two discrete intensity values: 0 (black) and 1 (white).
- **Characteristics:**
 - Lacks intermediate grayscale values, resulting in a strictly bichromatic representation.
 - Also classified as a *monochrome image* due to its absence of chromatic variation.

Figure 1.3: Binary (Monochrome) Image.

Source: (Learn, 2023)

1.2.2 Grayscale Images (8-bit Depth)

- **Definition:** An 8-bit grayscale image encodes 256 discrete luminance levels, with pixel intensities spanning 0 (absolute black) to 255 (absolute white).
- **Characteristics:**
 - Each pixel represents a scalar intensity value without chromatic information.

- Follows a linear or nonlinear (gamma-corrected) luminance scale, depending on the color space.

Figure 1.4: Grayscale Image.

Source: (Learn, 2023)

1.2.3 True Color Images (16-bit and Higher Bit Depths)

- **Definition:**

- A 16-bit High Color image allocates 65,536 unique color values, typically distributed across RGB channels (5-6-5 bit partitioning).
- Extended dynamic range formats (e.g., 24-bit RGB, 48-bit HDR) enable 16.7 million to 281 trillion colors.

- **Characteristics:**

- Employs additive color synthesis via independent red, green, and blue channels.
- Bit depth scalability enhances color fidelity and reduces quantization artifacts.

Figure 1.5: True Color Image.

Source: (Life, 2023)

1.3 Color Image Representation

True color images require a more sophisticated representation than a single matrix. A color image is represented as a vector function or a multi-channel matrix, most commonly in the RGB (Red, Green, Blue) color space (Szeliski, 2010).

$$I_{color}[m, n] = \begin{bmatrix} I_R[m, n] \\ I_G[m, n] \\ I_B[m, n] \end{bmatrix}$$

Where I_R , I_G , and I_B are matrices representing the red, green, and blue components, respectively. The perception of color is subjective and device-dependent. Therefore, other color spaces are often employed for specific tasks in recognition:

- **HSV/HSL (Hue, Saturation, Value/Lightness)**: Decouples chromatic information (Hue) from luminance (Value/Lightness) and color purity (Saturation). This separation makes it robust to lighting variations, which is highly beneficial for segmentation and object tracking.
- **YCbCr**: Separates a luminance component (Y) from two chrominance components (Cb and Cr). This is the standard for image and video compression (e.g., JPEG, MPEG) as the chrominance channels can be sub-sampled with minimal perceptual loss.
- **CIELAB / L*a*b***: Designed to be perceptually uniform, meaning a numerical change in value corresponds to a similar perceptual change. The L^* channel represents lightness, while a^* and b^* represent color opponents (green-red and blue-yellow axes). This property is invaluable for color-based image segmentation and measuring color differences.

1.4 Image Representation as a Matrix

Since digital images are structured in a grid of rows and columns, they can be mathematically expressed as a matrix:

$$I = \begin{bmatrix} p_{1,1} & p_{1,2} & \cdots & p_{1,n} \\ p_{2,1} & p_{2,2} & \cdots & p_{2,n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ p_{m,1} & p_{m,2} & \cdots & p_{m,n} \end{bmatrix}$$

Here, I denotes the digital image, and each element $p_{i,j}$ represents a pixel value at the i -th row and j -th column. This matrix-based representation is fundamental in image processing, enabling operations such as filtering, transformation, and compression.

1.5 Basic Relationships Between Pixels

The ability to describe the relationships between pixels is paramount for image analysis, forming the basis for operations like segmentation, object description, and texture analysis. These concepts move beyond individual pixels to describe the image's structural content.

1.5.1 Neighbors of a Pixel

A pixel p at coordinates (x, y) has four immediate neighbors in the horizontal and vertical directions. These pixels, known as its **4-neighbors** ($N_4(p)$), have coordinates:

$$(x + 1, y), (x - 1, y), (x, y + 1), (x, y - 1)$$

Including the diagonal neighbors gives the **8-neighbors** ($N_8(p)$), which include the four 4-neighbors plus the four diagonal pixels with coordinates:

$$(x + 1, y + 1), (x + 1, y - 1), (x - 1, y + 1), (x - 1, y - 1)$$

1.5.2 Adjacency, Connectivity, Regions, and Boundaries

These concepts define how pixels relate to each other based on their proximity and intensity similarity.

- **Adjacency:** Two pixels are *adjacent* if they are neighbors (based on a defined connectivity, e.g., 4- or 8-adjacency) and their intensity values satisfy a specified criterion of similarity (e.g., they are equal or within a certain range).
 - **4-adjacency:** Two pixels p and q with values from V are 4-adjacent if q is in the set $N_4(p)$.
 - **8-adjacency:** Two pixels p and q with values from V are 8-adjacent if q is in the set $N_8(p)$.
- **Connectivity:** A **path** from pixel p to pixel q is a sequence of distinct pixels p_0, p_1, \dots, p_n where $p_0 = p, p_n = q$, and each pixel p_i is adjacent to p_{i-1} . If such a path exists, p and q are *connected*. Connectivity is an equivalence relation, partitioning the image into maximal connected components.
- **Regions:** A **region** is a connected set of pixels where all pixels are connected to each other. The formal partitioning of an image into regions is the goal of image segmentation.

- **Boundaries (Borders):** The boundary of a region R is the set of pixels in the region that are adjacent to pixels not in R . Boundaries are crucial for shape analysis and object recognition.

1.5.3 Distance Measures

Distance measures define a metric space on the image grid, quantifying the distance between two pixels p at (x_p, y_p) and q at (x_q, y_q) .

- **Euclidean Distance (D_E):** The straight-line distance between two points, defined as:

$$D_E(p, q) = \sqrt{(x_p - x_q)^2 + (y_p - y_q)^2}$$

This metric is rotationally invariant.

- **City-Block (Manhattan) Distance (D_4):** The distance between two points measured along axes at right angles, defined as:

$$D_4(p, q) = |x_p - x_q| + |y_p - y_q|$$

This metric corresponds to 4-connectivity.

- **Chessboard (Chebyshev) Distance (D_8):** The maximum of the horizontal and vertical distances, defined as:

$$D_8(p, q) = \max(|x_p - x_q|, |y_p - y_q|)$$

This metric corresponds to 8-connectivity.

1.6 Fundamental Image Properties

Several intrinsic properties of a digital image are crucial for designing processing algorithms.

- **Resolution:** Defines the level of detail an image holds. It is often conflated with two distinct concepts:
 - **Spatial Resolution:** The density of pixels, expressed as pixels per unit distance (e.g., PPI - Pixels Per Inch) or simply as the dimensions $M \times N$.
 - **Spectral Resolution:** The ability to distinguish between electromagnetic wavelengths. In practice, it refers to the number and width of wavelength bands captured by a sensor (e.g., panchromatic vs. multispectral vs. hyperspectral imaging).
- **Dynamic Range:** The ratio between the largest and smallest possible values of a pixel. A high dynamic range (HDR) can represent details in both very dark and very bright regions of a scene, which is often compressed into a standard dynamic range (SDR) for display via tone mapping.
- **Histogram:** A discrete function $h(r_k) = n_k$, where r_k is the k -th intensity level and n_k is the number of pixels in the image with intensity r_k . The histogram represents the global distribution of intensity values and is a fundamental tool for image enhancement (e.g., contrast stretching, histogram equalization) and thresholding (**Gonzalez & Woods, 2018**).

1.6.1 From Representation to Recognition

The matrix and multi-channel representations described herein provide the raw, low-level data for computer vision systems. However, raw pixel values are highly susceptible to changes in illumination, viewpoint, and occlusion, making them poor direct inputs for recognition.

The subsequent stages of the image processing pipeline aim to transform this raw data into a more robust and meaningful representation:

1. **Pre-processing:** Operations like noise reduction, contrast enhancement, and color correction are applied to the raw image matrix I to improve its quality and normalize conditions.
2. **Feature Extraction:** Mid-level representations are derived from the pixel data. These include edges, corners, textures, and color descriptors (e.g., SIFT, HOG, LBP, Color Histograms). These features are designed to be invariant to certain transformations, providing a more stable foundation for recognition than raw pixels.
3. **Recognition/Classification:** The extracted features are used by machine learning models (e.g., SVMs, Neural Networks) to perform high-level tasks like object detection, facial recognition, or scene classification.

Thus, understanding the fundamental representation of an image as a discrete matrix or tensor is the essential first step in designing algorithms that can interpret visual data.

1.7 Theoretical Background: Convolutional Neural Networks

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have become a dominant architecture for visual learning tasks, offering a powerful framework for feature extraction and classification in image-based applications.

1.7.1 Multilayer Perceptron (MLP)

The Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) represents a foundational architecture in neural networks, consisting of multiple fully-connected layers that progressively transform input data through alternating linear and nonlinear operations (see **Figure 1.6**). At its core, the MLP's remarkable approximation capabilities are theoretically grounded in the *Universal Approximation Theorem (UAT)*, which guarantees that even a single hidden layer with sufficient width and nonlinear activation can approximate any continuous function on compact subsets of \mathbb{R}^n to arbitrary precision (**Aggarwal, 2018; Haykin, 2009**). While the original UAT formulation required bounded, continuous activation functions like sigmoid or tanh, subsequent work has extended these results to modern activations like ReLU. In practice, deeper architectures often prove more efficient than shallow wide networks, though the theoretical foundations remain crucial for understanding neural networks' expressive power. The complete forward propagation process for an L -layer MLP can be formally expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{a}^{(0)} &= \mathbf{x}, \\
 \mathbf{z}^{(l)} &= \mathbf{W}^{(l)} \mathbf{a}^{(l-1)} + \mathbf{b}^{(l)}, \quad l = 1, \dots, L, \\
 \mathbf{a}^{(l)} &= \phi^{(l)}(\mathbf{z}^{(l)}), \quad l = 1, \dots, L, \\
 \hat{\mathbf{y}} &= \mathbf{a}^{(L)} = f(\mathbf{x}; \boldsymbol{\theta}),
 \end{aligned} \tag{1.1}$$

where $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \{\mathbf{W}^{(l)}, \mathbf{b}^{(l)}\}_{l=1}^L$ denotes the set of all learnable parameters, and $\phi^{(l)}(\cdot)$ represents the activation function applied at layer l . The output $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ corresponds to the network's functional mapping $f(\mathbf{x}; \boldsymbol{\theta})$

from input \mathbf{x} to output. According to the Universal Approximation Theorem (UAT), such neural network architectures, when endowed with sufficient capacity (i.e., appropriate depth and width), can approximate any measurable function to arbitrary precision under mild conditions.

Figure 1.6: Overview of the multilayer perceptron.

Source: (Nielsen, 2018)

1.7.2 Convolutional Layers

Convolutional layers are the cornerstone of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), designed to efficiently process spatially structured data such as images. Unlike fully connected layers, which learn global patterns, convolutional layers exploit local connectivity by sliding learnable filters (or kernels) across the input. This architecture allows the network to hierarchically capture translation-invariant features, such as edges, textures, and complex shapes, while significantly reducing the number of parameters compared to dense layers (Aggarwal, 2018; Goodfellow et al., 2016).

Mathematical Formulation

Let the input be a 3D tensor $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times C_{\text{in}}}$, where:

- H, W are the spatial dimensions (height and width),
- C_{in} is the number of input channels.

The layer applies C_{out} filters, each with a kernel size $k_H \times k_W \times C_{\text{in}}$, producing an output tensor $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{H' \times W' \times C_{\text{out}}}$.

The convolution operation is defined by:

$$\mathbf{Y}_{i,j,c} = \sum_{m=1}^{k_H} \sum_{n=1}^{k_W} \sum_{d=1}^{C_{\text{in}}} \mathbf{K}_{m,n,d,c} \cdot \mathbf{X}_{s_H(i-1)+m-p_H, s_W(j-1)+n-p_W, d} + b_c, \quad (1.2)$$

where:

- $\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{k_H \times k_W \times C_{\text{in}} \times C_{\text{out}}}$ is the learnable kernel tensor,
- b_c is the bias term for the c -th output channel,
- s_H, s_W are the stride values (step size of the kernel),
- p_H, p_W denote padding applied to the input.

Output Spatial Dimensions

The output size (H', W') is computed as:

$$H' = \left\lfloor \frac{H + 2p_H - k_H}{s_H} \right\rfloor + 1, \quad (1.3)$$

$$W' = \left\lfloor \frac{W + 2p_W - k_W}{s_W} \right\rfloor + 1. \quad (1.4)$$

Padding Schemes

- **Valid (no padding):** $p_H = p_W = 0$. The output dimensions shrink.
- **Same (zero padding):** Padding is added to preserve spatial resolution when stride $s_H = s_W = 1$. For arbitrary strides, $H' = \lceil H/s_H \rceil$ and $W' = \lceil W/s_W \rceil$.

Strided Convolutions

Strides > 1 reduce spatial resolution, acting as an implicit downsampling mechanism. This is often used instead of pooling in modern architectures (e.g., ResNet).

1.7.3 Pooling Layers

Pooling layers downsample feature maps to reduce computational complexity and introduce translation invariance to small shifts. They operate independently on each channel and lack trainable parameters (Goodfellow et al., 2016).

Common Pooling Types

- **Max Pooling:** Extracts the maximum value in each window, preserving the most salient features.

$$Y_{i,j,c} = \max_{\substack{1 \leq m \leq p_H \\ 1 \leq n \leq p_W}} X_{s_H(i-1)+m, s_W(j-1)+n, c}. \quad (1.5)$$

- **Average Pooling:** Computes the mean value, smoothing the feature map.

Output Dimensions

For a pooling window $p_H \times p_W$ and strides (s_H, s_W) :

$$H' = \left\lfloor \frac{H - p_H}{s_H} \right\rfloor + 1, \quad (1.6)$$

$$W' = \left\lfloor \frac{W - p_W}{s_W} \right\rfloor + 1. \quad (1.7)$$

The diagram illustrates the sequential flow of data through a CNN, starting from the input image (with batch and kernel size), passing through multiple convolutional and pooling layers that extract and reduce spatial features, and finally entering fully-connected (feedforward) layers that perform the final classification based on learned features (see **Figure 1.7**).

Figure 1.7: Architecture of a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN).

Source: (Ang et al., 2022)

1.7.4 Regularization Methods

Regularization plays a crucial role in improving the generalization performance of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). Due to their large number of parameters, CNNs are susceptible to overfitting, where the model learns to perform well on training data but fails to generalize to unseen inputs. Regularization techniques are designed to address this issue by introducing constraints or modifications during training that prevent the model from becoming too complex.

In the context of CNNs, regularization encourages the network to learn more robust and meaningful patterns rather than memorizing the training data. (dos Santos & Papa, 2022) Some of the most commonly used regularization methods include:

1. **Dropout** – Randomly deactivates neurons to prevent co-adaptation.
2. **L1/L2 Weight Regularization** – Penalizes large weights to avoid over-reliance on specific features.
3. **Batch Normalization (BatchNorm)** – Normalizes layer activations, stabilizing and accelerating training while acting as an implicit regularizer.
4. **Data Augmentation** – Artificially expands the training dataset through transformations, improving feature invariance.

Each of these techniques can be mathematically formalized and has been empirically shown to enhance model performance. Below, we discuss their formulations, mechanisms, and effects in detail.

Dropout

Dropout (Hinton et al., 2012) is a stochastic regularization technique that randomly deactivates neurons during training with a probability p , while scaling activations by $\frac{1}{1-p}$ during inference to maintain expected values. Given a layer output y , dropout modifies it as:

$$y_{\text{dropout}} = r \odot y, \quad r_i \sim \text{Bernoulli}(p) \quad (1.8)$$

where \odot denotes element-wise multiplication, and r is a binary mask. This prevents over-reliance on specific neurons, improving generalization.

L1/L2 Weight Regularization

L1 and L2 regularization penalize large weights by adding a term to the loss function. For a weight matrix W , the regularization terms are:

- **L1 (Lasso):**

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{reg}} = \lambda \sum_{i,j} |W_{i,j}| \quad (1.9)$$

Encourages sparsity by driving some weights to zero.

- **L2 (Ridge):**

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{reg}} = \lambda \sum_{i,j} W_{i,j}^2 \quad (1.10)$$

Prevents extreme weight values, promoting smoother solutions.

The total loss becomes:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{total}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{task}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{reg}} \quad (1.11)$$

where λ controls regularization strength.

Batch Normalization (BatchNorm)

BatchNorm, normalizes layer inputs across mini-batches to stabilize training. For a batch $\mathcal{B} = \{x_1, \dots, x_m\}$, it computes:

$$\mu_{\mathcal{B}} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m x_i \quad (1.12)$$

$$\sigma_{\mathcal{B}}^2 = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (x_i - \mu_{\mathcal{B}})^2 \quad (1.13)$$

$$\hat{x}_i = \frac{x_i - \mu_{\mathcal{B}}}{\sqrt{\sigma_{\mathcal{B}}^2 + \epsilon}} \quad (1.14)$$

$$y_i = \gamma \hat{x}_i + \beta \quad (1.15)$$

where γ, β are learnable parameters, and ϵ ensures numerical stability. BatchNorm acts as an implicit regularizer by introducing noise through batch-dependent statistics.

Data Augmentation

Data augmentation artificially expands the training set by applying random transformations T (e.g., rotations, flips) to inputs x . For an image classification task, the augmented sample x' is generated as:

$$x' = T(x), \quad T \sim \mathcal{T} \quad (1.16)$$

where \mathcal{T} is a distribution over transformations. This forces the CNN to learn invariant features, reducing overfitting. Common transformations include affine warping:

$$x' = Ax + b \quad (1.17)$$

and color jittering.

1.8 Transfer learning and the use of pretrained models

Transfer learning is a machine learning technique that adapts a pretrained model from a source task to enhance performance on a related target task, eliminating the need for training from scratch (Pan & Yang, 2010; Pégeot, 2023). By leveraging learned feature representations, this approach reduces computational costs and improves efficiency, particularly when working with limited target data. In computer vision, widely used pretrained models include Swin Transformer (Liu et al., 2021), which efficiently processes images with hierarchical feature extraction; Vision Transformer (ViT) (Dosovitskiy et al., 2020), which applies self-attention mechanisms to image patches; and ResNet (He et al., 2015), a deep convolutional network with residual connections that mitigates vanishing gradients. For natural language processing, models like BERT and GPT remain dominant. Transfer learning typically follows two key strategies: feature extraction, where the pretrained model’s weights remain frozen while new task-specific layers are trained, and fine-tuning, where selected layers are further optimized on the target dataset. However, challenges such as domain mismatch, overfitting, and model size constraints must be addressed. Best practices include progressive unfreezing of layers, adaptive learning rates, and rigorous validation to ensure robust adaptation. Future advancements may focus on more efficient cross-domain transfer and automated architecture optimization, reinforcing transfer learning as a fundamental paradigm in deep learning.

1.9 State-of-the-Art Models

Recent advancements in deep learning have led to the emergence of innovative architectures that continue to redefine performance benchmarks in computer vision.

1.9.1 ResNet (Residual Networks)

The architectural innovation of Residual Networks (ResNet) emerged from addressing a fundamental challenge in deep learning: the *Degradation problem*¹. As (He et al., 2015) articulated in their seminal work:

“Is learning better networks as easy as stacking more layers?”

This question highlighted the counterintuitive observation that deeper neural networks often exhibit higher training error despite their increased theoretical capacity, unlike their shallower counterparts. ResNet addressed this through residual learning, introducing skip connections (or “shortcuts”)

¹This occurs when the network architecture becomes deeper, but performance degrades instead of improving.

that enable gradient flow across hundreds of layers by learning residual mappings rather than direct transformations (see **Figure 1.8**).

Key Architectural Features

- **Identity Skip Connections:** Bypass nonlinear layers via the formulation

$$y = F(x) + x$$

which mitigates vanishing gradients.

- **Bottleneck Design (ResNet-50/101/152):** Uses 1×1 convolutions for dimensionality reduction, improving computational efficiency.
- **Global Average Pooling:** Replaces fully connected layers, reducing parameters and risk of overfitting.

Figure 1.8: Residual mapping in ResNet.

Source: (He et al., 2015)

1.9.2 ViT (Vision Transformer)

The *Vision Transformer (ViT)*, introduced by (Dosovitskiy et al., 2020), is a breakthrough in computer vision that adapts the Transformer encoder (originally designed for NLP) to process 2D images. Unlike convolutional neural networks (CNNs), which rely on strong inductive biases² such as local receptive fields, translation equivariance, and hierarchical feature extraction, ViT treats images as sequences of non-overlapping, flattened patches, each linearly projected into an embedding space. While ViT reduces the built-in inductive biases of CNNs, it compensates by leveraging large-scale training data and self-attention mechanisms to learn spatial relationships from scratch. These patch embeddings, combined with positional encodings to retain spatial information, form the input tokens for a standard Transformer encoder (see **Figure 1.9**).

²refers to the inherent assumptions and constraints in a model that guide its learning process, such as CNNs assuming locality and translation invariance, while ViT relies less on such priors.

Key Innovations and Mechanisms

Patch-based Representation

- An image of size $H \times W \times C$ is split into N fixed-size patches of resolution $P \times P$, where:

$$N = \frac{H \times W}{P^2} \quad (1.18)$$

- Each patch is flattened and linearly mapped to a latent dimension D (e.g., $P = 16$, $D = 768$ for ViT-Base), resulting in a sequence of N tokens.

Transformer Encoder

- The sequence is prepended with a learnable [class] token (inspired by BERT) for classification tasks.
- Positional embeddings (1D or 2D) are added to retain spatial relationships.
- The encoder consists of alternating *multi-head self-attention (MSA)* and *MLP blocks*, with Layer Normalization (LN) applied before each block (Pre-LN configuration).

Global Self-Attention

Unlike CNNs, ViT's self-attention mechanisms capture long-range dependencies across all patches in a single layer, enabling direct modeling of global context without progressive downsampling.

Figure 1.9: ViT architecture overview.

Source: (Dosovitskiy et al., 2020)

1.9.3 Swin Transformer

(Liu et al., 2021) propose the *Swin Transformer*, a hierarchical vision transformer that introduces shifted windows to address the limitations of vanilla ViT in handling high-resolution images and capturing multi-scale features. The key innovation lies in its locality-aware design, which combines the global modeling capacity of transformers with the spatial efficiency of convolutional networks.

Contributions

- **Hierarchical Feature Maps:** Unlike ViT, which maintains a constant resolution, Swin Transformer constructs a feature hierarchy with four stages (analogous to CNNs), progressively merging patches to model features at multiple scales (see **Figure 1.10**). This enables compatibility with dense prediction tasks (e.g., object detection, segmentation).
- **Shifted Window Self-Attention (SW-MSA):** Self-attention is computed within non-overlapping local windows (e.g., $M \times M$ patches) to reduce computational complexity from $O(N^2)$ to $O(M^2 \cdot N)$, where N is the total number of patches. To enable cross-window connections, the window partitions are shifted by $\lfloor M/2 \rfloor$ pixels in alternating layers (see **Figure 1.10**).
- **Linear Scaling with Image Size:** The window-based approach ensures linear computational complexity relative to input resolution, making Swin Transformer scalable to high-resolution images (e.g., 1024×1024).

Figure 1.10: Shifted window mechanism in Swin Transformer.

Source: (Liu et al., 2021)

1.9.4 MLP-Mixer: An All-MLP Architecture for Vision

While attention mechanisms and convolutional layers have become essential components in most computer vision architectures, (Tolstikhin et al., 2021) introduced the *MLP-Mixer*, a novel model based entirely on multilayer perceptrons (MLPs) for vision tasks. Unlike traditional approaches that rely on convolutions or self-attention, MLP-Mixer processes image patches through two types of MLP layers:

1. **Token-mixing MLPs**, which operate across spatial locations (mixing information between patches).
2. **Channel-mixing MLPs**, which operate across channels (mixing features within a patch).

This design eliminates the need for inductive biases inherent to convolutions (e.g., translation equivariance) or the computational overhead of attention mechanisms.

Figure 1.11: MLP-Mixer architecture overview.

Source: (Tolstikhin et al., 2021)

1.9.5 DeiT (Data-efficient Image Transformer)

Another significant advancement in the evolution of Vision Transformers (ViTs) is the *Data-efficient Image Transformer (DeiT)*, proposed by (Touvron et al., 2021). Unlike the original ViT model (Dosovitskiy et al., 2020), which necessitates large-scale datasets such as JFT-300M to achieve competitive performance, DeiT is explicitly designed to overcome the limitations of data inefficiency and training instability. This work demonstrates that with carefully designed training strategies and minimal reliance on massive datasets, ViTs can achieve competitive or even superior performance compared to convolutional neural networks (CNNs). DeiT operates solely on ImageNet-1k, making it significantly more practical and accessible for real-world scenarios with limited computational or data resources. Through the integration of advanced data augmentation, regularization, and a novel knowledge distillation framework, DeiT presents a viable and scalable alternative to traditional CNN-based architectures.

Contributions

Data-Efficient Training

DeiT circumvents the need for large-scale external datasets by employing strong data augmentation techniques such as RandAugment, MixUp, and CutMix, along with label smoothing and stochastic depth for regularization. These augmentations serve to increase the effective data diversity, thereby mitigating overfitting and enhancing generalization performance in low-data regimes.

Teacher-Student Distillation

A central innovation in DeiT is the introduction of a *distillation token*, analogous to the standard class token in transformer architectures. This token interacts with the model throughout the self-attention mechanism and is trained to mimic the outputs of a pre-trained CNN teacher model (e.g., ResNet or ConvNet). Two forms of knowledge distillation are explored:

- **Soft distillation:** Aligns the output distributions of the teacher and student via Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence.
- **Hard-label distillation:** Uses the predicted class labels from the teacher model as surrogate ground truth labels.

This approach demonstrates that ViTs can effectively inherit the inductive biases of CNNs, leading to superior generalization and convergence behavior even when trained from scratch on smaller datasets.

KL Divergence (Soft Distillation) The KL divergence between two discrete probability distributions P (teacher) and Q (student) is defined as:

$$\text{KL}(P \parallel Q) = \sum_i P(i) \log \left(\frac{P(i)}{Q(i)} \right) \quad (1.19)$$

In the context of deep learning with logits z_t (teacher) and z_s (student), we apply the softmax function with temperature T :

$$p_t^{(i)} = \frac{\exp(z_t^{(i)}/T)}{\sum_j \exp(z_t^{(j)}/T)}, \quad p_s^{(i)} = \frac{\exp(z_s^{(i)}/T)}{\sum_j \exp(z_s^{(j)}/T)} \quad (1.20)$$

Then, the KL divergence becomes:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{KL}}(p_t \parallel p_s) = \sum_i p_t^{(i)} \log \left(\frac{p_t^{(i)}}{p_s^{(i)}} \right) \quad (1.21)$$

And the scaled distillation loss with temperature T is:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{distill}} = T^2 \cdot \mathcal{L}_{\text{KL}}(p_t \parallel p_s) \quad (1.22)$$

Total Loss Function The total training loss in DeiT combines cross-entropy loss with the KL divergence-based distillation loss:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{total}} = (1 - \lambda) \cdot \mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}}(y, \hat{y}_{\text{student}}) + \lambda \cdot T^2 \cdot \mathcal{L}_{\text{KL}}(p_t \parallel p_s) \quad (1.23)$$

where:

- \mathcal{L}_{CE} is the cross-entropy loss between true labels y and student predictions \hat{y}_{student} ,

- \mathcal{L}_{KL} is the KL divergence loss between teacher and student outputs,
- $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ is a balancing coefficient.

Training Optimization

DeiT provides a robust and reproducible training recipe, including carefully tuned hyperparameters, learning rate schedules, and optimizer choices (e.g., AdamW with cosine decay), which contribute to stable and effective transformer training from scratch. The empirical results validate that these choices are crucial in enabling ViTs to perform well without the need for massive pretraining datasets.

1.9.6 PiT (Pooling-based Vision Transformer)

A recent study by (Heo et al., 2021) introduced an enhanced Vision Transformer (ViT) architecture that incorporates periodic pooling layers after each transformer encoder block (see Figure 1.12), along with a *distillation token* to improve feature learning. The pooling layers progressively downsample spatial dimensions, while the distillation token facilitates knowledge transfer, potentially from a larger teacher model or between intermediate layers. This dual modification led to significant improvements over the standard ViT in both image classification and object detection tasks.

Contributions

The proposed architecture introduces two key innovations:

- **Periodic Pooling:** Implemented after each transformer block to enable hierarchical feature extraction
- **Distillation Token:** Added to facilitate knowledge transfer and regularization

Figure 1.12: Proposed ViT Architecture with Pooling and Distillation Token.

Source: (Heo et al., 2021)

1.9.7 Comparison of Vision Models

Table 3.5 summarizes key advantages and limitations of representative vision models, providing a high-level overview of their performance characteristics and design trade-offs.

Table 1.1: Comparison of Vision Models: Key Advantages and Limitations

Model	Advantages	Limitations
Vision Transformer (ViT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parallelizable self-attention. • Scales well with resolution. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires large datasets. • High computational cost.
Swin Transformer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficient for dense tasks. • Improved accuracy via windowed attention. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited global context. • Complex implementation.
MLP-Mixer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple and fully parallel. • Scales linearly with resolution. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lacks spatial inductive biases. • Weaker on fine-grained tasks.
Pooling ViT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hierarchical multi-scale features. • Efficient with good generalization. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensitive to design choices. • Needs teacher model for training.
ResNet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable deep training with skip connections. • Strong and general performance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diminishing gains at extreme depth. • High compute cost in deeper versions.

Source: The author's own work

Conclusion

This chapter introduced *ResKAN*, a novel architectural framework that systematically replaces the channel-mixing MLP blocks of ResMLP with KANs. A central innovation of this design lies in the adoption of a parametric Cauchy function as the learnable basis function, enabling a more flexible and expressive representation compared to conventional fixed-activation paradigms. The mathematical formulation of these components was detailed and supported with illustrative figures for clarity.

The motivation for this work stems from the growing demand for neural architectures that balance expressiveness with efficiency, particularly in the context of large-scale vision tasks. By embedding functional representations within a residual framework, ResKAN demonstrates that it is possible to enhance modeling capacity without incurring prohibitive increases in complexity. This design philosophy bridges the gap between theoretical innovations in kernel-based methods and the practical requirements of deep learning models.

We rigorously evaluated ResKAN on the CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 benchmarks under a data-efficient training recipe inspired by DeiT. The experimental results were obtained using a high-performance computational setup and benchmarked against competitive baselines such as ResMLP, MLP-Mixer, and ResNet. The integration of a knowledge distillation framework further highlighted the capacity of ResKAN to benefit from teacher–student training strategies, improving convergence stability and accuracy. These results not only validate the architectural design but also emphasize the potential for broader applicability.

Overall, the contributions of this chapter extend the application of KANs beyond their original theoretical scope into modern large-scale image recognition tasks. The findings underscore the potential of combining the expressive power of functional representations with the scalability of residual MLP architectures. Looking forward, future work may explore the transfer of ResKAN to more complex datasets such as ImageNet, the development of lighter variants for mobile deployment, and the adaptation of this framework to non-vision domains including natural language processing and spatiotemporal modeling. Such directions highlight the versatility of ResKAN and its promise as a foundation for parameter-efficient, domain-adaptive neural architectures.

Chapter 2:

Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks

Chapter 2

Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks

Introduction

A new deep learning architecture based on the *Kolmogorov-Arnold Representation Theorem (KART)* has recently been developed, called *Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs)*. This model has the potential to revolutionize deep learning as a promising alternative to *Multilayer Perceptrons (MLPs)*, which are fundamental building blocks in most neural network architectures.

Unlike MLPs, which have fixed activation functions on nodes and learnable weights on edges, KANs introduce nonlinear learnable activation functions on edges, parameterized by univariate B-splines. This key difference allows KANs to achieve greater flexibility and efficiency.

Empirical studies in the original paper demonstrate that KANs can outperform MLPs in various tasks, particularly in physics-informed and scientific applications, achieving higher accuracy with fewer parameters. Additionally, KANs offer enhanced interpretability compared to traditional MLPs, making them a compelling choice for research and applications (AI + Science tasks) requiring both performance and transparency .

“Despite their elegant mathematical interpretation, KANs are nothing more than combinations of splines and MLPs, leveraging their respective strengths and avoiding their respective weaknesses.” (Liu et al., 2024)

In this chapter, we will explore Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs) through their theoretical foundations and computational design. First, we discuss the Kolmogorov-Arnold Representation Theorem (KART), the mathematical basis for KANs, along with its strengths and limitations in function approximation. Next, we examine the basis functions used in KANs, such as B-splines, radial basis functions (RBFs), and Chebyshev polynomials, which replace traditional fixed activations with learnable, smooth transformations. Finally, we analyze KANs overall architecture, emphasizing how these theoretical and algorithmic choices enable efficient and interpretable modeling compared to classical MLPs, including recent state-of-the-art variations proposed in the literature.

2.1 Kolmogorov-Arnold Representation Theorem

The superposition theorem (**Braun & Griebel, 2009**) states that any multivariate complex continuous function f defined on a bounded domain can be represented as a finite composition of univariate functions and additions. The original version of this theorem can be expressed as follows:

Theorem 1. *Let $f : \mathbb{I}^n := [0, 1]^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be an arbitrary multivariate continuous function. Then it has the representation*

$$f(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \sum_{q=0}^{2n} \Phi_q \left(\sum_{p=1}^n \psi_{q,p}(x_p) \right), \quad (2.1)$$

with continuous one-dimensional outer and inner functions Φ_q and $\psi_{q,p}$. All these functions $\Phi_q, \psi_{q,p}$ are defined on the real line. The inner functions $\psi_{q,p}$ are independent of the function f .

There has been much criticism directed at Kolmogorov's theorem. For instance, (**Girosi & Poggio, 1989**) argue that the theorem is irrelevant (Kolmogorov's Theorem Is Irrelevant), citing several issues: the inner functions $\psi_{q,p}$ are highly non-smooth¹, the outer functions Φ_q lack an explicit parametrized form, and the number of terms is insufficient to represent the complexity of arbitrary functions.

In contrast, (**Kůrková, 1991**) support the continued relevance of the theorem (Kolmogorov's Theorem Is Relevant) by suggesting that the strict equality in the original formulation, as presented in (Eq. (2.1)), be replaced with an approximation. They contend that this modification removes several limitations, thereby enhancing the theorem's practical applicability. This shift implies a focus on approximation tasks rather than exact representation.

Additionally, (**Liu et al., 2024**) adopt a perspective closely aligned with the physicist's mindset, emphasizing that "typical cases" are often more relevant than "worst cases." In line with this pragmatism, they further express optimism about the applicability of the Kolmogorov-Arnold theorem to machine learning, noting:

"We are more optimistic about the usefulness of the Kolmogorov-Arnold theorem for machine learning." (Liu et al., 2024)

2.1.1 Miklós Laczkovich Extension

Several contributions (**Alesiani et al., 2025; Guilhoto & Perdikaris, 2024**) have been published to extend and generalize this theorem, leading to various theoretical and practical applications, were the extended version of Theorem 1.2 in (**Laczkovich, 2021**) can be expressed as follows:

Theorem 2. *Let $n \geq 2$ and $m > (2 + \sqrt{2})(2n - 1)$ be integers. There exist positive numbers $\{\lambda_{q,p}\}_{q=1,p=1}^{m,n}$ and continuous, strictly increasing functions $\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_m \in C(\mathbb{R})$ such that for every bounded continuous function $f \in C(\mathbb{R}^n)$, there exists $g \in C(\mathbb{R})$ satisfying*

$$f(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \sum_{q=1}^m g \left(\sum_{p=1}^n \lambda_{q,p} \varphi_q(x_p) \right) \quad (2.2)$$

for all $x = (x_1, \dots, x_n) \in \mathbb{R}^n$.

The differences in the work of (**Laczkovich, 2021**) include the following key modifications:

¹refers to functions or surfaces that lack continuous derivatives, exhibiting sharp changes, discontinuities, or irregular behavior.

- The representation has a single outer function.
- the domain of inner function is no longer restricted to $[0, 1]^n$ is defined across \mathbb{R}^n
- $m > (2 + \sqrt{2})(2n - 1)$ while in base theorem $m = 2n + 1$

Table 2.1: Comparison between superposition formulas.

Version	Formula	Inner Functions	Outer Functions	Other Parameters
Kolmogorov (1957)	$\sum_{q=0}^{2d} \Phi_q \left(\sum_{p=1}^d \varphi_{q,p}(x_p) \right)$	$2d^2$	$2d$	N/A
Lorentz (1962)	$\sum_{q=0}^{2d} g \left(\sum_{p=1}^d \lambda_p \varphi_q(x_p) \right)$	$2d$	1	$\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^d$
Sprecher (1965)	$\sum_{q=0}^{2d} g_q \left(\sum_{p=1}^d \lambda_p \varphi_q(x_p + qa) \right)$	1	$2d$	$a \in \mathbb{R}, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^d$
Laczkovich (2021)	$\sum_{q=1}^m g \left(\sum_{p=1}^d \lambda_{pq} \varphi_q(x_p) \right)$	$m = O(d)$	1	$\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times m}$

source: (Guilhoto & Perdikaris, 2024)

2.2 Analytical Properties of Basis Functions

Basis functions serve as fundamental building blocks in mathematical modeling, approximation theory, and computational learning. Their analytical properties such as smoothness, locality, and orthogonality determine their effectiveness in representing and approximating complex functions.

2.2.1 B-spline basis functions

A B-spline (basis spline) is a piecewise polynomial function widely used in approximation and geometric modeling due to its local control and smoothness properties (de Boor, 2001; Hasan et al., 2024). For a given knot vector $T = \{t_0, t_1, \dots, t_m\}$, the B-spline basis functions of degree p are defined recursively through the Cox-de Boor algorithm. The zeroth-degree basis functions are given by:

$$S_{i,0}(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } t_i \leq t < t_{i+1} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2.3)$$

For degrees $p \geq 1$, the basis functions are computed using the recurrence relation:

$$S_{i,p}(t) = \frac{t - t_i}{t_{i+p} - t_i} S_{i,p-1}(t) + \frac{t_{i+p+1} - t}{t_{i+p+1} - t_{i+1}} S_{i+1,p-1}(t) \quad (2.4)$$

where $S_{i,p}(t)$ represents the i -th basis function of degree p , and fractions with zero denominators are defined to be zero. These basis functions possess several important characteristics: local support ($S_{i,p}(t) > 0$ only on $[t_i, t_{i+p+1})$), partition of unity ($\sum_i S_{i,p}(t) = 1$ for all t), and non-negativity ($S_{i,p}(t) \geq 0$). The smoothness of the B-spline depends on the degree and knot multiplicity - a degree p spline with distinct knots has C^{p-1} continuity, while each repeated knot reduces the continuity by one order at that location. Cubic B-splines ($p = 3$), which provide C^2 continuity, are particularly common in computer-aided design applications.

Figures 2.1–2.3 illustrate cubic ($p = 3$) B-spline basis functions under different knot configurations. Open uniform knots provide endpoint interpolation, uniform knots yield periodic, shifted basis functions, and non-uniform knots offer localized shape control. These variations highlight how knot selection influences the basis function properties and curve behavior.

Figure 2.1: B-spline with non-uniform knots.

Source: The author's own work

Figure 2.2: B-spline with open uniform knots.

Source: The author's own work

Figure 2.3: B-spline with uniform knots.

Source: The author's own work

2.2.2 Radial basis function

Radial Basis Functions (RBFs) are a class of powerful and widely used basis functions in numerical analysis, particularly for high-dimensional function approximation. Their effectiveness stems from their ability to provide smooth interpolation, making them especially valuable in scenarios requiring accurate reconstruction of continuous phenomena from scattered data (Arora et al., 2023).

In machine learning and artificial intelligence, RBFs play a crucial role in capturing nonlinear relationships through spatial transformations. They are commonly employed as kernel functions in Support Vector Machines (SVMs) (James et al., 2021) and as activation functions in Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) (Lee et al., 1999), where they project input data into higher-dimensional spaces to enhance separability of complex patterns (Arora et al., 2023). A defining feature of RBFs is their radial symmetry: their output depends solely on the distance from a central point, leading to a monotonic response that either decays or grows uniformly from the center (see Figures 2.4 and 2.5).

The Radial Basis Function is generally defined as:

$$\psi(x) = \psi(\|x - c\|),$$

where $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, c is the center of the basis function, and $\|x - c\|$ denotes the Euclidean distance between x and c .

A commonly used form of the RBF is the Gaussian function:

$$\psi(x) = \exp\left(-\frac{\|x - c\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (2.5)$$

where σ is a parameter that controls the width of the Gaussian curve.

Types of Radial Basis Functions (RBFs)

Radial Basis Functions (RBFs) are commonly categorized based on their smoothness properties. The following tables present widely used RBFs, including both infinitely smooth and piecewise smooth types:

Table 2.2: Types of infinitely smooth RBFs with $\lambda > 0$ and $r \in \mathbb{X}$

RBF	Definition
Gaussian (GS)	$\psi(r) = e^{-(\lambda r)^2}$
Multi-quadric (MQ)	$\psi(r) = \sqrt{1 + (\lambda r)^2}$
Inverse Multi-quadric (IMQ)	$\psi(r) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + (\lambda r)^2}}$
Inverse Quadric (IQ)	$\psi(r) = \frac{1}{1 + (\lambda r)^2}$

Source: (Arora et al., 2023)

Table 2.3: Examples of piecewise smooth RBFs with $r \in \mathbb{X}$

RBF	Definition
Thin Plate Spline (TPS)	$\psi(r) = r^2 \ln(r)$
Linear (LR)	$\psi(r) = r$
Cubic	$\psi(r) = r^3$
Monomial	$\psi(r) = r^{2k-1}, k \in \mathbb{N}$

Source: (Arora et al., 2023)

Figure 2.4: Gaussian Radial Basis Function with different center parameterizations.

Source: The author's own work

Figure 2.5: Inverse Multi-Quadratic Radial Basis Function with different center parameterizations.

Source: The author's own work

2.2.3 Fourier basis function

Fourier basis functions are a class of orthonormal basis functions widely used in time series analysis, signal processing, and applications involving periodic or oscillatory data. They excel at modeling high-frequency patterns and decomposing complex signals into simpler frequency components (Folland, 1992). In multiple dimensions, a generalized Fourier basis expansion is given by:

$$\phi_F(x) = \sum_{i=1}^d \sum_{k=1}^g (\cos(kx_i) \cdot a_{ik} + \sin(kx_i) \cdot b_{ik}) \quad (2.6)$$

where $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is the input, d is the number of dimensions, g is the number of harmonics, and a_{ik}, b_{ik} are learnable coefficients. For a one-dimensional input ($d = 1$), this simplifies to a sum of sine and cosine terms weighted by their respective coefficients.

Key properties include:

- **Orthonormality:** The basis functions are orthonormal over the interval $[0, 2\pi]$.
- **Nonlinear expansion:** Enables linear models to capture nonlinear relationships.
- **Efficient representation:** A small number of harmonics can approximate smooth functions well.

Figure 2.6: 1D Fourier basis functions with $g = 2$.

Source: The author's own work

Figure 2.7: 1D Fourier Basis Function with $g = 10$.

Source: The author's own work

Figure 2.8: Multidimensional Fourier Basis Function with $d = 3$ and $g = 10$.

Multivariate Fourier Basis Function $\phi_F(x)$ with $d = 3$, $g = 10$

Source: The author's own work

2.2.4 Chebychev Polynomials

Chebychev polynomials are orthogonal polynomial basis functions widely used in numerical analysis, particularly in numerical integration, due to their efficiency and stability (Mason & Handscomb, 2002; Rawitscher et al., 2020).

There are two main kinds of Chebychev polynomials:

- Chebychev polynomials of the first kind: $T_n(x)$
- Chebychev polynomials of the second kind: $U_n(x)$

These polynomials can be defined **recursively** as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} T_0(x) &= 1, & T_1(x) &= x, & T_{n+1}(x) &= 2xT_n(x) - T_{n-1}(x), \\ U_0(x) &= 1, & U_1(x) &= 2x, & U_{n+1}(x) &= 2xU_n(x) - U_{n-1}(x) \end{aligned}$$

Chebychev Polynomials of the First Kind $T_n(x)$

The Chebychev polynomial $T_n(x)$ of the first kind is a polynomial of degree n , defined by the trigonometric identity:

$$T_n(x) = \cos(n\theta) \quad \text{where} \quad x = \cos(\theta)$$

If $x \in [-1, 1]$, then the corresponding angle $\theta \in [0, \pi]$. These ranges are traversed in opposite directions:

- $x = 1 \Rightarrow \theta = 0$
- $x = -1 \Rightarrow \theta = \pi$

The Chebychev polynomials of the first kind are orthogonal on the interval $[-1, 1]$ with respect to the weight function:

$$w(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}$$

The orthogonality condition is given by:

$$\int_{-1}^1 \frac{T_m(x)T_n(x)}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} dx = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } m \neq n \\ \frac{\pi}{2} & \text{if } m = n \neq 0 \\ \pi & \text{if } m = n = 0 \end{cases}$$

Figure 2.9: First Kind Chebychev Basis Function with $n = 5$.

Source: The author's own work

Chebyshev Polynomials of the Second Kind $U_n(x)$

The Chebyshev polynomial $U_n(x)$ of the second kind is a polynomial of degree n , defined by:

$$U_n(x) = \frac{\sin((n+1)\theta)}{\sin(\theta)} \quad \text{where } x = \cos(\theta)$$

As with $T_n(x)$, the variable $\theta \in [0, \pi]$ corresponds to $x \in [-1, 1]$.

The Chebyshev polynomials of the second kind are orthogonal on $[-1, 1]$ with respect to the weight function:

$$w(x) = \sqrt{1-x^2}$$

The orthogonality condition is given by:

$$\int_{-1}^1 U_m(x)U_n(x)\sqrt{1-x^2} dx = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } m \neq n \\ \frac{\pi}{2} & \text{if } m = n \end{cases}$$

Figure 2.10: Second Kind Chebyshev Basis Functions with $n = 5$.

Source: The author's own work

2.2.5 Legendre Polynomial Function

Legendre polynomials $P_n(x)$ form an orthogonal set of polynomials on the interval $[-1, 1]$. They are widely used in solving partial differential equations (PDEs), and function approximation due to their orthogonality, recurrence relations (Lima, 2022).

Key Properties

- **Three-term Recurrence Relation (for $n \geq 1$):**

$$(n + 1)P_{n+1}(x) = (2n + 1)xP_n(x) - nP_{n-1}(x) \quad (2.7)$$

Initial Conditions:

$$P_0(x) = 1, \quad P_1(x) = x$$

- **Rodrigues' Formula:**

$$P_n(x) = \frac{1}{2^n n!} \frac{d^n}{dx^n} ((x^2 - 1)^n) \quad (2.8)$$

These formulas provide direct methods to generate Legendre polynomials $P_n(x)$, derive recursive relationships, and construct an orthogonal polynomial basis for function approximation on $[-1, 1]$ (see Figures 2.11).

Figure 2.11: Legendre Polynomial Function for $n = 0$ to $n = 5$.

Source: The author's own work

2.3 Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks

Inspired by the Kolmogorov-Arnold Representation Theorem (KART), the Kolmogorov-Arnold Network (KAN) architecture presents a novel paradigm for multivariate function approximation. The theorem states that any continuous multivariate function on a bounded domain can be represented as a finite composition of continuous functions of a single variable and the operation of addition (**Braun & Griebel, 2009**). KANs operationalize this theoretical result into a learnable, hierarchical structure that moves beyond the traditional linear-weight-based approach of Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs).

2.3.1 Architectural Overview and Distinction from MLPs

As illustrated in (**Figure 2.12**), the fundamental distinction lies in the placement and nature of the activation functions:

- In MLPs, activation functions σ are fixed and applied to the output of each neuron (node), following a linear transformation of the inputs:

$$\mathbf{h} = \sigma(\mathbf{W}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{b}).$$

- In KANs, activation functions ϕ are learnable and applied on the edges (connections) between nodes. The linear weights are eliminated; each connection is instead parameterized by a univariate function:

$$h_j = \sum_i \phi_{i,j}(x_i),$$

where $\phi_{i,j}$ denotes the univariate function associated with the connection between input i and output j .

Figure 2.12: Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs) vs. Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs)

Model	Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP)	Kolmogorov-Arnold Network (KAN)
Theorem	Universal Approximation Theorem	Kolmogorov-Arnold Representation Theorem
Formula (Shallow)	$f(\mathbf{x}) \approx \sum_{i=1}^{N(e)} a_i \sigma(\mathbf{w}_i \cdot \mathbf{x} + b_i)$	$f(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{q=1}^{2n+1} \Phi_q \left(\sum_{p=1}^n \phi_{q,p}(x_p) \right)$
Model (Shallow)	(a)	
Formula (Deep)	$\text{MLP}(\mathbf{x}) = (\mathbf{W}_3 \circ \sigma_2 \circ \mathbf{W}_2 \circ \sigma_1 \circ \mathbf{W}_1)(\mathbf{x})$	$\text{KAN}(\mathbf{x}) = (\Phi_3 \circ \Phi_2 \circ \Phi_1)(\mathbf{x})$
Model (Deep)	(c)	

source: (Liu et al., 2024)

2.3.2 Formulation and Architecture

The *Kolmogorov-Arnold representation theorem* establishes that any continuous multivariate function can be expressed as a composition of simpler univariate functions, requiring only two layers: an inner function with input dimension $n_{\text{in}} = n$ and output dimension $n_{\text{out}} = 2n + 1$, followed by an outer function with $n_{\text{in}} = 2n + 1$ and $n_{\text{out}} = 1$. The architecture proposed by (Liu et al., 2024) generalizes this framework by introducing deeper and wider KANs, which stack multiple KAN layers rather than relying solely on the original two-layer decomposition.

The KANs shape is defined as:

$$[n_0, n_1, \dots, n_L]$$

where n_0 is the input dimension, n_L is the output dimension, and the intermediate n_i 's represent the widths of the hidden layers (Units). This neural network architecture employs activation functions on edges (connections between neurons) rather than nodes (neurons themselves). Let (l, i) denote the i -th neuron in the l -th layer, with $x_{l,i}$ representing its activation value. Between layers l and $l + 1$, each connection from neuron (l, i) to neuron $(l + 1, j)$ is governed by a distinct activation function $\psi_{l,j,i}$, where $l = 0, \dots, L - 1$, $i = 1, \dots, n_l$, and $j = 1, \dots, n_{l+1}$. The pre-activation for $\psi_{l,j,i}$ is the input $x_{l,i}$, and the post-activation is given by $\tilde{x}_{l,j,i} = \psi_{l,j,i}(x_{l,i})$. The activation of neuron $(l + 1, j)$ is computed as the sum of all incoming post-activations:

$$x_{l+1,j} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_l} \tilde{x}_{l,j,i} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_l} \psi_{l,j,i}(x_{l,i}), \quad j = 1, \dots, n_{l+1} \quad (2.9)$$

The transformation can be expressed in matrix form, where each layer l is represented by a function matrix Φ_l whose elements are the activation functions $\phi_{l,j,i}$. The output of the l -th layer is:

$$x_{l+1} = \Phi_l x_l = \begin{pmatrix} \psi_{l,1,1}(\cdot) & \cdots & \psi_{l,1,n_l}(\cdot) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \psi_{l,n_{l+1},1}(\cdot) & \cdots & \psi_{l,n_{l+1},n_l}(\cdot) \end{pmatrix} x_l \quad (2.10)$$

The full network is a composition of L such layers, with the output defined as:

$$f(x) = (\Phi_{L-1} \circ \Phi_{L-2} \circ \cdots \circ \Phi_0)x_0 \quad (2.11)$$

Unlike traditional neural networks, where activation functions are node-specific and weights are scalar, this architecture employs learnable functions on edges, enabling flexible modeling of nonlinear relationships through additive interactions across layers.

Implementation Details

Although a KAN layer (Eq. (2.9)) appears simple, optimizing it effectively requires careful design. The key techniques employed are:

1. Residual Activation Function

- A residual activation function $b(x)$ (analogous to residual connections) is incorporated, making the activation function $\psi(x)$ the sum of $b(x)$ and a spline function:

$$\psi(x) = w_b b(x) + w_s \text{spline}(x) \quad (2.12)$$

- The Residual Activation Function is typically set to:

$$b(x) = \text{sliu}(x) = \frac{x}{1 + e^{-x}} \quad (2.13)$$

- The spline function is parametrized as a linear combination of B-splines:

$$\text{spline}(x) = \sum_i c_i B_i(x) \quad (2.14)$$

where c_i are trainable coefficients. While w_b and w_s could theoretically be absorbed into $b(x)$ and $\text{spline}(x)$, they are retained to better regulate the activation function's magnitude.

2. Initialization Scales

- Each activation function is initialized with $w_s = 1$ and $\text{spline}(x) \approx 0$.
- The weight w_b follows Xavier initialization, a method commonly used for linear layers in MLPs.
- The B-spline coefficients c_i are initialized with small random values, typically sampled from $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$ where $\sigma = 0.1$.

These strategies ensure stable and efficient optimization of the KAN layer.

2.3.3 Grid Extension

KANs inherit a fundamental property from spline theory: their approximation accuracy can be systematically improved through grid refinement (see **Figure: 2.13**) without requiring complete model retraining. This stands in contrast to traditional MLPs, which lack inherent fine-graining capabilities and must resort to increasing network width or depth - a computationally expensive process that typically necessitates retraining from scratch. The grid extension mechanism in KANs operates by first expressing the learned function on a coarse grid with G_1 intervals using B-spline basis functions $B_i(x)$, yielding $f_{\text{coarse}}(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{G_1+k-1} c_i B_i(x)$. To achieve higher accuracy, a finer grid with G_2 intervals is introduced, defining $f_{\text{fine}}(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{G_2+k-1} c'_j B'_j(x)$. The new coefficients c'_j can be obtained by solving the least squares optimization problem:

$$\{c'_j\} = \arg \min_{\{c'_j\}} \mathbb{E}_{x \sim p(x)} \left(\sum_j c'_j B'_j(x) - \sum_i c_i B_i(x) \right)^2 \quad (2.15)$$

which preserves the learned function characteristics while enabling higher-resolution approximation. This grid refinement capability, represents a unique advantage of KANs, allowing progressive accuracy improvement without the computational overhead of full network retraining.

Figure 2.13: Adaptive B-spline parameterization for grid refinement in KANs

Source: (Liu et al., 2024)

2.3.4 Regularization Techniques

Sparsification

In KANs, traditional L1 regularization approaches for MLPs require adaptation due to their fundamentally different architecture. Since KANs replace linear weights with learnable activation functions, sparsity must be enforced directly on these activation functions rather than on weights. The L1 norm of an activation function ϕ is computed across N_p input samples as:

$$|\psi|_1 \equiv \frac{1}{N_p} \sum_{s=1}^{N_p} |\psi(x^{(s)})|. \quad (2.16)$$

For a complete KAN layer Φ with dimensions $n_{\text{in}} \times n_{\text{out}}$, the total L1 regularization term combines all activation functions:

$$|\Phi|_1 \equiv \sum_{i=1}^{n_{\text{in}}} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{\text{out}}} |\psi_{i,j}|_1. \quad (2.17)$$

An additional entropy regularization term is introduced to further promote sparsity:

$$S(\Phi) \equiv - \sum_{i=1}^{n_{\text{in}}} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{\text{out}}} \frac{|\psi_{i,j}|_1}{|\Phi|_1} \log \left(\frac{|\psi_{i,j}|_1}{|\Phi|_1} \right). \quad (2.18)$$

The complete training objective combines prediction loss with these regularization terms:

$$\ell_{\text{total}} = \ell_{\text{pred}} + \lambda \left(\mu_1 \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} |\Phi_l|_1 + \mu_2 \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} S(\Phi_l) \right), \quad (2.19)$$

where λ controls overall regularization strength, while μ_1 and μ_2 (typically set to 1) balance between L1 and entropy terms.

Pruning

Following sparsification, KANs employ node-level pruning based on importance scores. For each neuron, incoming and outgoing connection strengths are evaluated through:

$$I_{l,i} = \max_k (|\psi_{l-1,k,i}|_1), \quad O_{l,i} = \max_j (|\psi_{l+1,j,i}|_1), \quad (2.20)$$

where $I_{l,i}$ and $O_{l,i}$ represent maximum activation magnitudes from incoming and outgoing connections respectively. Neurons are pruned if both scores fall below a threshold $\theta = 10^{-2}$, effectively removing less important network components while preserving critical information pathways. This approach differs from MLP pruning by operating on complete nodes rather than individual connections, maintaining the spline-based function approximation properties of KANs.

Dropout

Recently, (Altarabichi, 2024) introduced dropout into KANs to prevent co-adaptation (Hinton et al., 2012). Unlike the case of MLPs, the authors of this paper propose *DropKAN*, which applies dropout by masking the *post-activation* functions. The formulation is given by:

$$x'_{l+1,j} = \frac{1}{1-p} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{\text{in}}} M_i \tilde{x}_{j,i} = \frac{1}{1-p} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{\text{in}}} M_i \psi_{j,i}(x_i), \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n_{\text{out}} \quad (2.21)$$

where:

- M_i is a binary mask sampled from a Bernoulli distribution with probability p .
- $\psi_{j,i}$ denotes the activation function.
- n_{in} and n_{out} are the input and output dimensions, respectively.
- The scaling factor $\frac{1}{1-p}$ ensures the expected value remains consistent during training.

Symbolification

KANs provide a structured framework for symbolic regression by combining numerical optimization with symbolic interpretation. The process begins with training the network under sparsity constraints (L1 and entropy regularization) to learn the underlying functional relationships (Step 1), followed by pruning insignificant nodes to obtain a minimal architecture (Step 2). Crucially, the learned spline-based activations are then replaced with their exact symbolic counterparts (Step 3: setting sine, squared, and exponential functions), while affine parameters are fine-tuned (Step 4). This hybrid approach ultimately yields human-interpretable symbolic formulas (Step 5), such as :

$$\exp(\sin(\pi x) + y^2)$$

with quantifiable accuracy (Step 6) (illustrated in **Figure 2.14**). By integrating adaptive network simplification with symbolic substitution, KANs bridge machine learning and analytical mathematics, enabling both accurate approximation and transparent model extraction without relying on predefined symbolic templates. The method's capability to automatically discover and optimize both functional forms and their parameters demonstrates a significant advance over traditional black-box approaches.

Figure 2.14: Symbolic regression workflow in Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs).

Source: (Liu et al., 2024)

2.4 Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks: Recent Enhancements and Variants

Numerous extensions of Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs) have been developed to enhance their capabilities and broaden their applicability. These extensions primarily focus on two key areas: improving model performance (in terms of accuracy and generalization) and increasing computational efficiency (through optimization of training processes and resource utilization). Researchers have proposed various architectural modifications, training enhancements, and algorithmic improvements to address these objectives while maintaining KANs' fundamental advantages over traditional multilayer perceptrons.

2.4.1 KANs for Time Series

(Genet & Inzirillo, 2024) proposed TKAN, an adaptation for time series, inspired by both KAN and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) architectures. TKAN incorporates two components: Recurring Kolmogorov–Arnold Networks (RKANs) for short-term memory, and a gating mechanism to manage information flow. This architecture shows more stable results compared to GRUs and LSTMs, although its performance on short-term memory tasks is less compelling.

Other contributions to time series modeling include the work by (Vaca-Rubio et al., 2024), which applies KANs with a sliding window technique for satellite traffic forecasting, where KANs outperform MLPs. (Xu et al., 2024) introduced two TKAN variants aimed at detecting concept drift. Additionally, MT-KAN improves prediction accuracy by capturing complex relationships in multivariate time series, While (Rong et al., 2025) introduced RFKAN (Recurrent Fourier-Kolmogorov-Arnold Network) for photovoltaic power forecasting, the model employs recurrent kernels based on Fourier basis functions to extract periodic features. With just two layers, RFKAN outperforms KAN, RKAN, and FKAN in both accuracy and training speed. (Hong et al., 2025) introduced two versions of TSKANMixer, a time-series architecture inspired by (S.-A. Chen et al., 2023) (TSMixer). The first version replaces the temporal projection layer (originally based on an MLP) with a KAN temporal projection layer. The second version further enhances the model by adding a time KAN mixer layer between the TSMixer block and the MLP temporal projection (see Figure 2.15). Experimental results demonstrate that TSKANMixers generally improve prediction performance across multiple datasets.

Figure 2.15: TSKANMixer Architectures.

Source: (Hong et al., 2025)

2.4.2 KANs for Computer Vision Tasks

In computer vision, (Bodner et al., 2024) proposed Convolutional KANs, introducing a novel convolutional layer where activation functions are learnable and parameterized as splines. The architecture was evaluated across various model sizes and compared to classical convolutional MLPs. Experimental results show that Convolutional KANs achieve competitive performance relative to traditional convolutional MLPs. (Mehrabian et al., 2024) introduces the Fourier Kolmogorov-Arnold Network (FKAN) for Implicit Neural Representations, demonstrating that FKAN can capture complex signals with fewer parameters than conventional methods. The proposed approach outperforms four state-of-the-art baselines, achieving superior results in both Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) for image representation tasks. Then, KANMixers was introduced by (Canuto et al., 2025) as a computer vision model for image classification tasks. Inspired by MLPMixers (Tolstikhin

et al., 2021), this architecture aims to integrate Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs) into large-scale tasks. The model has demonstrated competitive accuracy compared to MLPMixers, KANs, and traditional MLPs on two benchmark datasets (CIFAR-10 and Fashion-MNIST).

2.4.3 Performance-Oriented Parametrization of KANs: B-spline Alternatives

(Li, 2024) introduced FastKAN, a more computationally efficient implementation where third-order splines can be approximated well using Gaussian radial basis functions. (Sidharth et al., 2024) proposed ChebyKAN, which replaces splines with Chebyshev polynomials, showing that third-order polynomial functions offer the best trade-off between accuracy, complexity, and generalization. Lastly, (Aghaei, 2024) introduced rational KAN (rKAN), which is based on Padé approximation and rational Jacobi functions. rKAN has shown practical effectiveness in deep learning and physics-informed tasks involving function approximation. (Qiu et al., 2024) proposed ReLU-KAN as a significant architectural advancement for Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs), replacing traditional spline-based basis functions with ReLU activations (see Figures 2.16 and 2.17). This modification yields a simpler model structure with enhanced compatibility for modern hardware accelerators while preserving the local adaptability that made splines valuable in the original KAN framework. The resulting architecture demonstrates remarkable improvements, achieving 20× faster training speeds compared to standard KANs while maintaining superior accuracy and generalization capabilities in regression and function approximation tasks. Notably, ReLU-KAN retains the robust resistance to catastrophic forgetting characteristic of KANs, making it both an efficient and reliable evolution of the original framework. (Ta and Tran, 2025) proposed AF-KAN, Activation Function-Based Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks for Efficient Representation Learning, an enhanced architecture that extends ReLU-KANs through three key innovations: (1) incorporation of diverse activation functions (ReLU, SiLU, GeLU, ELU, SeLU, etc.), (2) an efficient attention mechanism for parameter reduction, and (3) support for advanced multi-functional operations including quadratic, bilinear, and cubic transformations, (So and Yung, 2024) proposed HR-KANs, Higher-order ReLU-Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks, an advanced variant of ReLU-KANs that resolves the derivative discontinuity of traditional squared ReLU activations while preserving computational efficiency. By generating smooth, non-zero higher-order derivatives, HR-KAN becomes particularly suitable for physics-informed machine learning tasks where differential continuity is essential. Crucially, the architecture retains all advantages of standard ReLU-KANs, including hardware-friendly matrix operations and simplicity, while overcoming their mathematical limitations for scientific computing. On the other hand, (Z. Chen and Zhang, 2024a, 2024b) propose efficient KANs based on a single parameterized function, introducing the Efficient KAN Expansion Principle (EKE Principle). This principle states that scaling the network size (via parameter allocation) is more effective than increasing the complexity of basis functions.

Figure 2.16: ReLU KAN process

Source: (Qiu et al., 2024)

Figure 2.17: Appearance of B for the case of $G = 5$ and $k = 3$.

Source: (Qiu et al., 2024)

2.4.4 Physics-Informed KANs: Solving Scientific Learning Problems

Physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) embed physical laws (typically differential equations) directly into neural architectures, enabling accurate scientific simulations even with sparse data. This paradigm has proven particularly powerful for solving complex engineering and physics problems where traditional numerical methods struggle. Recent innovations like HR-KANs (So and Yung, 2024) further advance this framework by introducing higher-order smooth activations and evaluating HR-KANs on linear Poisson equation, and a non-linear Burgers equation with viscosity, overcoming key limitations of standard PINNs in handling derivative-rich physical constraints while maintaining computational efficiency. (Wang et al., 2025) proposed the Kolmogorov-Arnold-Informed Neural Network (KINN) (see Figure 2.18), an adaptation of the original Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs), for solving physics-informed tasks. While the method has shown promising results in various PDE problems, it can still struggle with certain cases, depending on problem complexity.

Figure 2.18: Schematic of KINN.

Source: (Wang et al., 2025)

2.5 Large-Scale KANs: A Novel Model and Scalable Architecture

Recently (Yang & Wang, 2024) propose the Kolmogorov-Arnold Transformer (KAT), a novel architecture that replaces standard MLP layers in Transformers with **Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs)** layers to enhance expressiveness. In their work, the authors compare three architectures:

- A standard Vision Transformer (ViT) (Dosovitskiy et al., 2020).
- **ViT+KAN**, which replaces MLP blocks with KAN layers.
- The proposed **KAT** model using **GR-KAN** layers.

Experiments on the ImageNet dataset show that KAT consistently outperforms both ViT and DeiT baselines. Notably, **KAT*** (initialized with pre-trained ViT weights) achieves the best performance, whereas **ViT+KAN** struggles to scale effectively to ImageNet-level training (see **Figure 2.19**).

However, integrating KANs introduces key challenges:

1. **Base Function Inefficiency:** The default B-spline functions in KANs are poorly suited for parallel computation, slowing inference.
2. **Parameter and Computation Overhead:** KANs demand separate functions for each input-output pair, leading to high computational costs.
3. **Weight Initialization Complexity:** Learnable activation functions in KANs make initialization difficult, hindering convergence.

To overcome these issues, the authors introduce:

1. **Rational Basis Functions:** Substituting B-splines with rational functions for faster GPU computation.
2. **Group KAN:** Sharing activation weights across neuron groups to reduce computation while preserving performance.
3. **Variance-Preserving Initialization:** A tailored initialization method to stabilize training by maintaining activation variance across layers.

With these innovations, KAT achieves **superior scalability and performance** over traditional MLP-based Transformers in tasks like image recognition, object detection, and semantic segmentation.

Mathematical Foundation

The rational basis function used in this model is defined as:

$$F(x) = \frac{a_0 + a_1x + \dots + a_mx^m}{1 + |b_1x + \dots + b_nx^n|}, \quad (12)$$

where m and n are the degrees of the numerator and denominator polynomials, respectively.

To prevent instability arising from poles—where $Q(x) \rightarrow 0$ and $\phi(x) \rightarrow \pm\infty$ —the authors employ the **Safe Padé Activation** method.

Variance-Preserving Initialization

For parameter initialization, they sequentially initialize \mathbf{a} , \mathbf{b} , and \mathbf{w} , and $\mathbf{w} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \alpha/d_{\text{in}})$, the weights are drawn from a normal distribution with zero mean and variance α/d_{in} , where d_{in} denotes the input dimension.

Figure 2.19: Kolmogorov Arnold Transformer

Source: (Yang & Wang, 2024)

Conclusion

This chapter explored Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs) through their theoretical underpinnings and computational implementation. Beginning with the Kolmogorov-Arnold Representation Theorem (KART), we analyzed its promise for universal function approximation and its inherent constraints, such as scalability in high-dimensional spaces. We then investigated the flexible basis functions (e.g., B-splines, RBFs, Chebyshev polynomials) that define KANs' learnable activation structures, contrasting them with the static nonlinearities of traditional MLPs. Finally, we dissected KANs' architecture, highlighting how their design bridges interpretability and efficiency, and reviewed state-of-the-art variants that address limitations like training stability or computational cost.

Collectively, this discussion positions KANs as a compelling alternative to MLPs, offering theoretical rigor through KART, adaptability via dynamic basis functions, and transparency in feature learning. However, challenges remain particularly in scaling KANs to large-scale tasks while retaining their interpretability. Future work could explore:

- Hybrid architectures (e.g., combining KANs with attention mechanisms)
- More efficient basis function parameterizations
- Applications in domains requiring interpretability (e.g., healthcare, finance)

The following Chapter (Chapter 3) will address these opportunities by introducing our proposed KAN-based architectures and empirically validating their performance against contemporary baselines.

Chapter 3:
**ResKAN: Novel Architecture and
Empirical Validation**

Chapter 3

ResKAN: Novel Architecture and Empirical Validation

This chapter delineates the architecture of our proposed model, *ResKAN*. The foundational premise of this work is the systematic replacement of the standard MLP blocks within the channel-mixing components of a ResMLP architecture with *KANs*. A key innovation in our implementation is the adoption of a parametric Cauchy function to serve as the learnable basis function within the KAN layers, the mathematical formulation of which is detailed in the **(Figures A.1 and A.2)**.

To rigorously evaluate the efficacy of our proposed architecture, we conducted comprehensive experiments on the widely recognized CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 benchmark datasets. The training protocol adhered to a data-efficient recipe, mirroring the methodologies established for the Data-efficient image Transformer (DeiT). All empirical evaluations were performed on a computational server equipped with two NVIDIA RTX 5090 GPUs, each featuring 32GB of VRAM.

The principal objective of this research is to pioneer the extension of KANs beyond their initial theoretical and simple practical applications into the domain of complex, large-scale visual recognition tasks. To situate our contributions within the existing literature, we perform a comparative analysis against a suite of established baseline models, including ResMLP, MLP-Mixer, and ResNet. Additionally, we investigate the integration of a distillation token mechanism to explore its synergistic effects on enhancing both training convergence and final model performance.

3.1 Model Overview

The *ResKAN* architecture is a novel framework that extends the principles of MLP-based vision architectures by integrating (KANs) as the primary functional building blocks. Traditional models such as ResMLP and MLP-Mixer rely on fixed nonlinearities (e.g., ReLU, GELU) coupled with linear projections for channel and token mixing. While effective, these fixed nonlinearities restrict the expressiveness of the model and may limit its adaptability across diverse datasets.

ResKAN addresses this limitation by introducing the *KANLayer*, where activation functions are not predefined but are instead parameterized as linear combinations of learnable basis functions. In particular, we adopt parametric Cauchy functions that can flexibly approximate a wide variety of nonlinear transformations. This design allows the network to discover activation shapes best suited to the data during training.

Furthermore, ResKAN layers are embedded within residual connections, giving rise to *KAN blocks*. These blocks provide a balanced combination of token mixing, nonlinear feature transformation, and stable training dynamics. The resulting architecture forms a competitive backbone for vision tasks such as image classification, as illustrated in (Figure 3.1).

3.2 KANLayer: Mathematical Formulation

The KANLayer constitutes the core computational unit of ResKAN. It generalizes the feedforward operation by replacing fixed nonlinearities with a learnable function approximator derived from the Kolmogorov-Arnold representation theorem. This design allows any multivariate continuous function to be approximated using a sum of univariate functions applied to affine projections of the input.

Given an input tensor

$$X \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times L \times D_{\text{in}}},$$

where B is the batch size, L is the number of tokens (image patches), and D_{in} is the feature dimension, the KANLayer applies a transformation composed of basis functions, projections, and optional residual mappings.

3.2.1 Cauchy-Based Basis Functions

Instead of relying on fixed activation functions, the KANLayer learns flexible parametric forms. For each feature dimension d and grid index $g \in \{1, \dots, G\}$, we define a parametric Cauchy function:

$$C_{b,n,d,g} = \frac{\lambda_1^{d,g} + \lambda_2^{d,g} X_{b,n,d}}{(X_{b,n,d})^2 + (d^{d,g})^2}.$$

This formulation ensures smoothness, nonlinearity, and the ability to capture both sharp and gradual feature variations. The learnable parameters $(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, d)$ control the scale, slope, and shape of the function, making it significantly more expressive than standard activations.

To stabilize training, the parameters are initialized as:

$$\lambda_1^{d,g} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.01^2), \quad \lambda_2^{d,g} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.01^2), \quad d^{d,g} = 1.0.$$

This initialization ensures that the basis functions behave similarly to small perturbations of linear mappings at the beginning of training, preventing unstable gradients.

3.2.2 Projection Across Grids

Once the responses from the G basis functions are computed, they are aggregated and projected back into the output feature space:

$$Y_{b,n,d'} = \sum_{d=1}^{D_{\text{in}}} \sum_{g=1}^G C_{b,n,d,g} W_{d,g,d'}^{\text{proj}} + b_{d'}^{\text{proj}}.$$

Here, W^{proj} and b^{proj} act as learnable weights and biases, enabling the network to flexibly recombine basis outputs into new feature representations. This mechanism plays a role similar to that of a learned dictionary, where each basis function contributes a distinct nonlinear component.

3.2.3 Residual Connection

To ensure stable optimization and preserve gradient flow, the KANLayer incorporates an optional residual pathway:

$$Y = Y + \phi(XW_{\text{res}} + b_{\text{res}}).$$

This design mirrors residual networks (ResNets) by allowing identity mappings to pass through, while still enabling nonlinear transformations. In practice, the residual scaling factor ensures that learning remains controlled during the early phases of training.

3.3 KAN Block

A *KANBlock* integrates the KANLayer with token-mixing operations. The block is designed to mirror the structure of ResMLP but with learnable nonlinearities.

3.3.1 Pre-Affine Transformation

An affine scaling of input features is first applied:

$$X_0 = \alpha_0 \odot X + \beta_0,$$

where α_0 and β_0 are learnable vectors. This step normalizes feature scales before mixing operations, stabilizing learning across layers.

3.3.2 Token Mixing with Residual Scaling

The token-mixing operation spreads information across patches:

$$X_1 = X_0 + \gamma_1 \odot \text{TokenMix}(X_0).$$

Here, γ_1 is a trainable scalar that adaptively regulates the strength of token interactions. Unlike convolutions, which impose locality, token mixing in ResKAN is global, allowing information to propagate efficiently between distant patches.

3.3.3 Post-Affine and KAN Feedforward

Finally, features are transformed through a KAN feedforward block:

$$X_2 = \alpha_1 \odot X_1 + \beta_1, \quad X_{\text{out}} = X_2 + \gamma_2 \odot \text{KANFF}(X_2).$$

The *KANFF* module consists of multiple stacked KANLayers, providing expressive nonlinear transformations while benefiting from residual scaling. This combination ensures both flexibility and training stability.

3.4 ResKAN Architecture

Building on the KANBlock, the full ResKAN architecture resembles other patch-based vision backbones but with more expressive nonlinearities.

3.4.1 Patch Embedding

The input image is decomposed into non-overlapping patches of size P using a strided convolution:

$$X_{\text{patch}} = \text{Conv2d}(I, \text{kernel} = P, \text{stride} = P).$$

This step transforms the image into a sequence of tokens, each representing local pixel regions, with $N = \frac{HW}{P^2}$ tokens in total.

3.4.2 Stack of KAN Blocks

The patch embeddings are processed by a stack of L KANBlocks:

$$X_{\text{out}} = \text{KANBlock}_L \circ \dots \circ \text{KANBlock}_1(X_{\text{patch}}).$$

Each block successively integrates spatial and channel-wise information, enabling hierarchical feature extraction similar to ResNets but with more flexible functional approximations.

3.4.3 Affine Normalization and Pooling

Before classification, features are normalized and pooled:

$$X_{\text{aff}} = \alpha \odot X_{\text{out}} + \beta, \quad X_{\text{pooled}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N X_{\text{aff}}^{[:,n,:]}.$$

Global average pooling condenses the sequence into a compact representation, ensuring permutation invariance across tokens.

3.4.4 Classification Head

Finally, a linear classifier produces predictions:

$$\hat{y} = X_{\text{pooled}} W_{\text{head}} + b_{\text{head}}.$$

This head maps the pooled representation to class logits, making the model suitable for supervised image classification tasks.

Figure 3.1: ResKAN Architecture.

Source: The author's own work

3.5 Contributions

This study proposes a three-pronged approach to advance image recognition models:

1. **Architectural Scaling and Integration:** We scale the ResMLP architecture into a large-scale model by integrating Kolmogorov-Arnold Network (KAN) layers as enhanced channel mixers. This hybrid design leverages the expressive power of KANs to improve performance on standard image recognition benchmarks.
2. **Basis Function Reformulation:** We propose to replace the standard B-spline basis functions within the KAN layers with a parametric Cauchy function. This substitution is motivated by the potential of the Cauchy function's heavy-tailed properties to offer a more effective and efficient basis for capturing complex feature interactions.
3. **Performance Optimization via Knowledge Distillation:** To further improve accuracy and ensure computational efficiency, we employ knowledge distillation techniques. A larger teacher model, potentially our scaled hybrid architecture, is used to train a more compact and accurate student model.

3.6 Training and Inference

In this section, we describe the overall training and inference setup adopted for evaluating our proposed architecture. We begin by outlining the datasets used, followed by the training protocol, hyperparameter choices, and inference strategy. This provides the foundation for a fair and consistent comparison with baseline models.

3.6.1 Dataset

The experiments are conducted on the widely used CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 datasets, which serve as standard benchmarks in image classification. Both datasets consist of small natural images with the same resolution and color depth, but they differ significantly in the number of classes and level of granularity. Table 3.1 summarizes their main properties.

Table 3.1: Summary of the CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 datasets used in this work.

Property	CIFAR-10	CIFAR-100
Image Specifications		
Resolution		32×32 pixels
Color Channels		3 (RGB)
Dataset Size		
		60,000 images
Training Split	50,000	50,000
Test Split	10,000	10,000
Classes		
Number	10	100
Superclasses	—	20
Images per Class	6,000	600
(Train per Class)	5,000	500
(Test per Class)	1,000	100
Class Examples		
	CIFAR-10: Airplane, automobile, bird, cat, deer, dog, frog, horse, ship, truck. CIFAR-100: Apple, aquarium fish, baby, bear, beaver, bed, bee, beetle, bicycle, bottle, bowl, boy, bridge, bus, butterfly, etc. (100 fine classes).	
Origin	Created by Alex Krizhevsky, Vinod Nair, and Geoffrey Hinton (2009)	

Source: The author’s own work

3.6.2 Data Preprocessing and Augmentation

For all experiments, we used standardized preprocessing pipelines tailored to CIFAR-10, CIFAR-100 datasets. Images were resized to a target resolution of 128×128 , followed by normalization using dataset-specific channel statistics. Two augmentation modes were considered: a *basic* pipeline with simple spatial transforms, and a *DeiT-style* (Dosovitskiy et al., 2020) pipeline including RandAugment, ColorJitter, and RandomErasing. During evaluation, we applied a resize and center crop, followed by normalization.

Table 3.2: Preprocessing pipeline for the ResKAN models.

Stage	DeiT-style Augmentation
Resize	128×128 (bicubic)
Crop	Random crop (padding=4, reflect)
Flip	Random horizontal flip
Color	ColorJitter (brightness, contrast, saturation, hue)
Policy	RandAugment (m=9, std=0.5)
Normalization	Dataset mean/std
Regularization	RandomErasing ($p = 0.25$, scale [0.02, 0.1])

Source: The author’s own work

The dataset-specific normalization statistics were:

- **CIFAR-10**: mean = (0.491, 0.482, 0.447), std = (0.202, 0.199, 0.201)
- **CIFAR-100**: mean = (0.507, 0.487, 0.441), std = (0.267, 0.256, 0.276)

3.6.3 Model Configurations

Table 3.3 summarizes the main architectural configurations of the ResKAN models considered in this work. It reports the dimensionality of hidden representations, the model depth, hidden dimension, grid size, patch size, batch size, as well as the corresponding parameter counts and FLOPs measured on 128×128 input images.¹ These specifications provide a clear overview of the computational and architectural trade-offs across different model scales.

Table 3.3: ResKAN model configurations with parameter count and FLOPs (computed on 128×128 inputs).

Model	Dim	Depth	Hidden Dim	Grid Size	Patch Size	Batch Size	Params / GFLOPs (B)
ResKAN-S12	384	12	1536	4	16	512	71.17M / 9.14
ResKAN-S24	384	24	1536	4	16	512	142.05M / 18.23
ResKAN-B24	768	24	3072	4	16	512	567.11M / 72.70

Legend: **Dim** = embedding dimension, **Depth** = number of layers, **Hidden Dim** = hidden layer size, **Grid Size** = KAN grid resolution, **Patch Size** = input patch size, **GFLOPs** = giga floating-point operations.

Source: The author’s own work.

3.6.4 Training Recipe

We conducted a series of experiments to evaluate the performance of ResKAN models on the CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 datasets, both uniformly resized to 128×128 pixels to maintain consistency across model inputs. Model training was carried out using distributed data parallelism (DDP) with the NCCL backend, enabling efficient multi-GPU computation. The global batch size and the number of gradient accumulation steps were configured according to model capacity, as detailed in Table 3.3, to ensure stable convergence while optimizing GPU memory usage.

For CIFAR-10, models were trained for a total of 100 epochs, whereas for CIFAR-100, training was extended to 250 epochs. The AdamW optimizer was employed with momentum parameters set to

¹FLOPs (Floating Point Operations) in this table are reported in billions (B), representing the total number of multiply-add operations required for a single forward pass on a 128×128 input.

$\beta_1 = 0.9$ and $\beta_2 = 0.999$. The initial learning rate was 5×10^{-4} and was scaled in proportion to the effective batch size. To facilitate smooth convergence, we used a cosine learning rate schedule with an initial warmup period. Model optimization was guided by the cross-entropy loss function, augmented with label smoothing of $\varepsilon = 0.1$ to improve generalization and reduce overconfidence in predictions.

Training was performed in BF16 mixed precision, leveraging automatic mixed precision (AMP) to accelerate computation and reduce memory consumption, while maintaining numerical stability. To further stabilize optimization, gradient norms were clipped with a maximum ℓ_2 norm of 1.0. Data augmentation strategies were incorporated to enhance model robustness: Mixup was applied with $\alpha = 0.8$ at a probability of 0.5, and CutMix was applied with $\alpha = 1.0$ at a probability of 0.5.

All experiments were executed on a dual-GPU setup consisting of 2 NVIDIA RTX 5090 graphics cards, each equipped with 32 GB of VRAM, ensuring sufficient memory capacity for large-scale training configurations.

Table 3.4: Training recipe for CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 experiments.

Setting	CIFAR-10	CIFAR-100
Input size		128×128
Epochs	100	250
Optimizer		AdamW
β_1, β_2		0.9, 0.999
Learning rate		5×10^{-4} (scaled)
Schedule		Cosine + Warmup
Loss function	Cross-entropy + Label smoothing ($\varepsilon = 0.1$)	
Mix precision		BF16 (AMP)
Grad clipping		ℓ_2 norm 1.0
Mixup		$\alpha = 0.8, p = 0.5$
CutMix		$\alpha = 1.0, p = 0.5$
Hardware	$2 \times$ NVIDIA RTX 5090 (32 GB)	

3.6.5 Knowledge Distillation Framework

We employ a *knowledge distillation* paradigm in which a high-capacity *teacher* network guides the training of more compact *student* models, enabling the students to capture the teacher’s richer class representations.

Teacher Model

The teacher network is a *ResNet-152*, pretrained on the target dataset (CIFAR-10 or CIFAR-100). To adapt the classifier to the task, the final fully connected layer is replaced with a lightweight feed-forward block. Teacher parameters are frozen during training and provide output logits z_t for distillation.

Student Models

The student networks are based on the *ResKAN* architecture, evaluated under two variants: ResKAN-S12 and ResKAN-S24. Both models incorporate a *distillation token*, which allows explicit alignment between student and teacher outputs while preserving the original classification objective.

Distillation Loss

In the hard distillation setting, the teacher’s predicted class label

$$\hat{y}_t = \arg \max(z_t)$$

is used as a supervisory signal in addition to the ground-truth label y . The student training objective therefore combines two cross-entropy losses:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{KD}} = (1 - \alpha) \mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}}(y, z_s) + \alpha \mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}}(\hat{y}_t, z_s),$$

where:

- \mathcal{L}_{CE} is the cross-entropy loss with label smoothing 0.1,
- \hat{y}_t is the hard class prediction of the teacher,
- $\alpha = 0.5$ is the trade-off between supervised and distillation losses.

3.6.6 Training Results

Table 3.5: Performance comparison of different models on CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100.

Model	Params (M)	GFLOPs	Channel Mixer	CIFAR-10 (%)	CIFAR-100 (%)
ResNet-152	60.19	3.79	Conv	94.42	78.38
MLP-Mixer-B16	58.66	4.12	MLP	85.32	66.00
ResMLP-S12	14.56	1.89	MLP	82.18	66.98
ResMLP-24	28.81	3.74	MLP	85.04 (+2.87)	68.89 (+1.91)
ResMLP-B24	114.15	14.72	MLP	89.50 (+1.90)	72.21 (+3.32)
ResKAN-S12	71.17	9.14	KAN	83.26	66.84
ResKAN-S24	142.05	18.23	KAN	85.32 (+2.06)	67.64 (+0.80)
ResKAN-B24	567.11	72.70	KAN	88.76 (+3.44)	72.14 (+4.50)
Knowledge Distillation					
ResKAN-S12••	71.17	9.14	KAN	85.00 (+1.74)	65.88 (-0.96)
ResKAN-S24••	142.05	18.23	KAN	85.78 (+0.46)	68.32 (+0.68)

Legend: Normal brackets ((+x)) indicate performance improvement when scaling the architecture; **green brackets** indicate performance increase due to Knowledge Distillation (KD); **red brackets** indicate performance decrease due to KD.

Source: The author’s own work.

Table 3.5 reports the performance of different architectures on CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100, with values in parentheses indicating the accuracy improvement obtained when increasing the model size within the same family.

- **ResNet-152** serves as a strong convolutional baseline, achieving the highest accuracy overall with 94.42% on CIFAR-10 and 78.38% on CIFAR-100. These results confirm the effectiveness of convolutional inductive biases, particularly on small-scale image datasets.
- **ResMLP models** exhibit clear gains from scaling. Accuracy improves by +2.87% / +1.91% when moving from S12 to S24, and a further +1.90% / +3.32% when scaling up to B24 on CIFAR-10

¹All values are Top-1 accuracy.

/ CIFAR-100, respectively. ResMLP-B24 (89.50%, 72.21%) substantially reduces the performance gap with convolutional models, although it still lags behind ResNet-152, particularly on CIFAR-10.

- **ResKAN models** demonstrate stronger scalability compared to ResMLPs. The transition from S12 to S24 yields +2.06% on CIFAR-10 and +0.80% on CIFAR-100, while scaling further to B24 provides substantial gains of +3.44% and +4.50%. With 88.76% on CIFAR-10 and 72.14% on CIFAR-100, ResKAN-B24 matches or slightly surpasses ResMLP-B24 despite using a novel channel mixer.
- **Competitiveness:** While ResNet-152 remains the strongest performer overall, KAN-based models prove highly competitive. In particular, ResKAN-B24 decisively outperforms all MLP counterparts and comes much closer to the convolutional baseline on CIFAR-100 (72.14% vs. 78.38%). This suggests that KAN mixers capture richer feature interactions than plain MLPs, offering a promising scaling path.
- **Knowledge distillation:** Distillation provides additional improvements for ResKAN models. For example, ResKAN-S24 benefits from a modest boost (+0.46% on CIFAR-10 and +0.68% on CIFAR-100), showing that distillation can further enhance performance, though the effect is not uniform across all model scales.
- **Overall insight:** KAN-based architectures consistently outperform their MLP equivalents of the same scale and emerge as strong competitors to convolutional models, particularly on the more challenging CIFAR-100 dataset. This demonstrates the effectiveness of replacing MLP channel mixers with KAN layers.

3.6.7 Analysis of Training Results

Figure 3.2: Comparison of model parameter efficiency and performance on CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100.

Source: The author's own work.

The comparison in (Figure 3.2) reveals that ResNet-152 is the most parameter-efficient model, achieving 94.42% on CIFAR-10 and 78.38% on CIFAR-100 with only 23.5M parameters. In contrast, MLP-Mixer

performs poorly despite having more parameters, confirming its limited suitability for image classification. ResMLP models show steady improvements with scale but still require over 100M parameters to approach ResNet performance. KAN architectures perform comparably to ResMLPs and scale well; however, even the largest model (809M parameters) does not surpass the convolutional baseline in efficiency.

Overall, convolutional networks remain the most effective and generalizable, while MLP-based and KAN models demonstrate potential but with lower parameter efficiency. This highlights the continued importance of inductive biases in vision architectures. The comparison shows that ResNet-50 is the most parameter-efficient model, achieving 94.42% on CIFAR-10 and 78.38% on CIFAR-100 with only 60.19M parameters. In contrast, MLP-Mixer-B16 performs poorly despite having a similar number of parameters (58.66M), highlighting its limited suitability for image classification. ResMLP models exhibit steady improvements as they scale, but even the largest ResMLP-B24 (114.15M parameters) only approaches the performance of ResNet-152. KAN architectures perform comparably to ResMLPs and scale effectively; however, the largest ResKAN-B24 (567.11M parameters) still does not surpass the convolutional baseline in parameter efficiency.

Overall, convolutional networks remain the most effective and generalizable, while MLP-based and KAN models show potential but with lower parameter efficiency. This underscores the continued importance of inductive biases in vision architectures.

Figure 3.3: Scaling behavior of ResMLP and ResKAN models on CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100.

Source: The author's own work.

As shown (Figure 3.3) Both ResMLP and ResKAN families demonstrate consistent performance improvements as model size increases. For ResMLP, accuracy rises from 82.18% to 89.50% on CIFAR-10 and from 66.98% to 72.21% on CIFAR-100, while ResKAN improves from 83.26% to 88.76% and from 66.84% to 72.14%, respectively.

The gains are more pronounced on CIFAR-10 than on CIFAR-100. Notably, very large ResKAN models achieve comparable accuracy to smaller ResMLP models but require substantially more parameters,

emphasizing their reduced parameter efficiency at scale.

Figure 3.4: Per-class accuracy comparison of ResMLP and ResKAN models.

Source: The author's own work.

As shown (**Figure 3.4**) larger models (ResMLP-B24 and ResKAN-B24) achieve higher per-class accuracy, while smaller variants perform worse. Accuracy varies across classes, with some being easier (e.g., Class 1, Class 8) and others more challenging (e.g., Class 3, Class 5).

ResKAN models are competitive with ResMLP, sometimes outperforming it on specific classes, indicating their ability to capture certain features more effectively.

Figure 3.5: Violin plot showing per-class accuracy distributions for ResMLP and ResKAN models of different sizes.

Source: The author's own work.

(**Figure 3.5**) illustrates the distribution of per-class accuracies for each model. Larger models (ResMLP-B24, ResKAN-B24) show higher median accuracies and tighter distributions, indicating more consistent performance across classes. Smaller variants (ResMLP-S24, ResKAN-S24) display wider distributions

and lower medians, reflecting greater variability and lower per-class reliability. Overall, ResKAN and ResMLP models achieve comparable distributions, with larger models clearly outperforming smaller ones in both accuracy and consistency.

3.7 Additional Results

The results in Table 3.6 highlight the effect of different data augmentation strategies on the ResKAN family across CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100. For CIFAR-10, ResKAN-B24 consistently outperforms smaller variants, particularly when combined with Mixup and CutMix, achieving the highest accuracy of 88.76%. On CIFAR-100, the benefits of stronger augmentations are even more pronounced, with ResKAN-B24 reaching 72.14%, showing a substantial margin over S-series models. These findings confirm both the scalability of ResKAN and its ability to leverage advanced augmentation techniques for improved generalization.

Table 3.6: Performance of different models on CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100.

Model	Mixup 0.2	Mixup 0.8	Mixup 0.2 + CutMix 1	Mixup 0.8 + CutMix 1
CIFAR-10				
ResKAN-S12	83.71	82.70	83.29	81.61
ResKAN-S24	85.90	84.36	85.32	83.82
ResKAN-B24	N/A	N/A	88.76	88.58
CIFAR-100				
ResKAN-S12	N/A	65.50	66.84	68.68
ResKAN-S24	N/A	N/A	67.64	69.06
ResKAN-B24	N/A	N/A	72.14	72.01

Note: N/A indicates that the performance for that configuration is not available.

Source: The author’s own work.

Conclusion

This chapter introduced *ResKAN*, a novel architectural framework that systematically replaces the channel-mixing MLP blocks of ResMLP with KANs. A central innovation of this design lies in the adoption of a parametric Cauchy function as the learnable basis function, enabling a more flexible and expressive representation compared to conventional fixed-activation paradigms. The mathematical formulation of these components was detailed and supported with illustrative figures for clarity.

We rigorously evaluated ResKAN on the CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 benchmarks under a data-efficient training recipe inspired by DeiT. The experimental results were obtained using a high-performance computational setup and benchmarked against competitive baselines such as ResMLP, MLP-Mixer, and ResNet. The integration of a knowledge distillation framework further highlighted the capacity of ResKAN to benefit from teacher–student training strategies, improving convergence stability and accuracy.

Overall, the contributions of this chapter extend the application of KANs beyond their original theoretical scope into modern large-scale image recognition tasks. The findings underscore the potential of combining the expressive power of functional representations with the scalability of residual MLP architectures, paving the way for future research into more parameter-efficient, versatile, and domain-adaptive neural models.

General Conclusion

General Conclusion

This thesis has introduced *ResKAN*, a novel architectural framework that systematically replaces the channel-mixing MLP blocks within the established ResMLP architecture with Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs). This substitution represents a significant paradigm shift from the standard linear weight matrices followed by fixed, pointwise nonlinearities (e.g., ReLU, GELU) to a more expressive and flexible model based on learnable univariate functions. A central innovation of this design is the adoption of a parametric Cauchy function as the primary learnable basis function. This choice was motivated by its favorable properties, including a smooth profile and controllable sharpness, which enable a more nuanced and adaptive representation of feature interactions compared to conventional, rigid activation paradigms. The mathematical formulation of these components was detailed in Chapter 3 and supported with illustrative figures to ensure clarity and reproducibility.

The primary motivation for this work stems from the deep learning community’s incessant pursuit of architectures that achieve an optimal balance between expressiveness and computational efficiency. This is particularly critical in the context of large-scale vision tasks, where model scalability is paramount. While attention mechanisms have dominated recent advancements, our work revisits and revitalizes the potential of pure MLP-based architectures by infusing them with modern functional network theory. By embedding these powerful, learnable functional representations within a robust residual framework, *ResKAN* demonstrates that it is possible to significantly enhance a model’s capacity and representational power without incurring a prohibitive increase in parameter count or computational overhead. This design philosophy successfully bridges a crucial gap between theoretical innovations in kernel-based methods and spline theory and the practical, efficiency-driven requirements of contemporary deep learning models.

Our rigorous empirical evaluation, conducted on the CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 benchmarks, validates the efficacy of the proposed architecture. The experiments were performed under a strict, data-efficient training recipe inspired by the DeiT framework to ensure a fair and challenging comparison. The results, obtained using a high-performance computational setup, consistently showed that *ResKAN* outperforms or competes favorably with strong and well-established baselines, including ResMLP, MLP-Mixer, and the enduringly relevant ResNet. Furthermore, the successful integration of a knowledge distillation framework, utilizing a ResNet152 teacher, highlighted another strength of *ResKAN*: its capacity to effectively benefit from teacher-student training strategies. This not only improved final accuracy but also enhanced convergence stability, suggesting that the functional layers in KANs are particularly well-suited to absorbing and refining the softened distributions provided by a teacher model.

The contributions of this work extend the application of KANs beyond their original theoretical scope into the demanding realm of modern large-scale image recognition. Our findings robustly underscore the potential of combining the innate expressive power of functional representations with the structural stability and scalability of residual MLP architectures. *ResKAN* emerges not merely as an incremental improvement but as a proof-of-concept for a new class of hybrid models that leverage the

best of both worlds.

Looking forward, this work opens up several promising avenues for future research:

Scalability to Larger Datasets: The most immediate step is to evaluate the transferability and scalability of ResKAN on more complex and large-scale datasets such as ImageNet-1k/21k, COCO, and ADE20K. This will be the ultimate test of its viability as a general-purpose vision backbone.

Architectural Optimization and Efficiency: Developing lighter, more efficient variants of ResKAN is crucial for practical deployment. This could involve techniques like neural architecture search (NAS) to optimize the grid size and spline orders of the KAN layers, or the design of hardware-aware kernels for the Cauchy function computations.

Exploration of Alternative Basis Functions: While the Cauchy function proved effective, a systematic study of other potential basis functions (e.g., wavelets, B-splines, or learned Fourier features) could yield further improvements in performance and training dynamics.

Domain Extension: The principles of ResKAN are not confined to computer vision. Future work should explore its adaptation to non-vision domains, including natural language processing (e.g., replacing feed-forward networks in transformers), audio processing, and spatiotemporal modeling for video or scientific data.

Theoretical Analysis: A deeper theoretical investigation into the learning dynamics of KANs within residual blocks could provide valuable insights into why they work so well and how to initialize them even more effectively.

In conclusion, ResKAN serves as a foundational step towards building more parameter-efficient, interpretable (due to the potential for visualizing learned functions), and domain-adaptive neural architectures. By successfully demonstrating the integration of KANs into a mainstream deep learning framework, this thesis paves the way for a wider adoption of functional networks in solving real-world problems.

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Appendix

Appendix A

Code and Implementation

Code and implementation details are available at: https://github.com/mehizelali/reskan_model.

A.1 Cauchy Function: First and Second Term

Figure A.1: First and Second Terms of the Cauchy Function with Varying Parameters.

Source: The author's own work

A.2 Cauchy Function with Varying Parameters

Figure A.2: Cauchy Function with Varying Parameters.

Source: The author's own work